

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH
AND MODELLING

D9.11 Final outreach report

Project

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Authors	Eliza Jordan, TRI Zainab Mehdi, TRI
Contributors	Corinna Pannofino, TRI Su Anson, TRI Hannah Robinson, UANTWERPEN Carla Ventre, SAPIENZA James Rhys Edwards, SINUS Viktoria Adler, SYNYO Neda Deneva, SYNYO Jose Manuel Palma Oliveira, FS Beatriz Rosa, FS Diana Beljaars, SU Sergei Shubin, SU Niamh Aspell, TRI Beki Hooper, TRI

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	Javier Lorente , URJC Marina Ghersetti , UGOT Bengt Johansson , UGOT Ioannis Bagkatzounis , KEMEA Anna Tsekoura , KEMEA Ioannis Konstantopoulos , KEMEA Effrosyni Dima , KEMEA
Reviewers	Corinna Pannofino , TRI Su Anson , TRI

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the COVINFORM project's communication activities conducted throughout the duration of the project. The deliverable recaps the Communication Plan (as outlined in D9.2 Communication Plan) and the update of the Communication Plan conducted in M18 (D9.7 Communication Plan – update M18).

As COVINFORM produced outputs from M3 on (in the form of bi-monthly reports), dissemination started more or less simultaneously with communication. As such, there was a close alignment between dissemination and communication activities, while keeping in mind their different aims.

The aim of the project's communication plan was to ensure appropriate activities were undertaken to inform, engage, create awareness, and promote information about the project, its aims, its funding source, its results, impacts and wider societal implications. It introduces strategic and targeted measures to inform the media and the general public about the project and its results as well as promote them and showcase the project's impact. It defines key messages to the project's target audiences and stakeholders (e.g., benefits that the project provides to each stakeholder), and appropriate communication channels and instruments to communicate them including newsletters, social media, and mass media.

COVINFORM adopted a multi-channel, multi-layered communication strategy that is designed to promote the project and its activities, as well as key insights to the different target audiences. The project engaged its audiences via a multitude of channels. While some of these were forms of one-way communication (for example, via factsheets and press releases), partners also aimed to gather feedback and knowledge exchange with the stakeholders (for example, via active engagement with stakeholders on social media).

As a living document, this communication plan was adapted, updated, and adjusted throughout the project's lifetime.

Revision notes M36

The deliverable maps out the communication activities conducted during the project's lifespan and compares these to the communication strategy and KPIs set out at the beginning of the project (and revised in M18). In addition, we unpick the learnings, best practices, and challenges in engaging with stakeholders resulting from the project. By doing so, it is hoped that these learnings will help future projects implement successful communication and outreach strategies.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
BAME	Black and Ethnic Minority
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DoA	Description of Action
EAB	Expert & Advisory Board
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

1 Introduction

The aim of the project's communication plan was to ensure appropriate activities were undertaken to inform, engage, create awareness, and promote information about the project, its aims, its funding source, its results, impacts and wider societal implications. It introduced strategic and targeted measures to inform the media and the public about the project and its results as well as promote them and showcase the project's impact. It defined key messages to the project's target audiences and stakeholders (e.g., benefits that the project provides to each stakeholder) and appropriate communication channels and instruments to communicate them, including newsletters, social media, and mass media. COVINFORM aimed to engage its audiences via a multitude of channels. While some of these were forms of one-way communication (for example, via factsheets and press releases), partners also aimed to gather feedback and knowledge exchange with the stakeholders (for example, via active engagement with stakeholders on social media). The communication plan also provided guidance to the COVINFORM partners, aiming to align their activities along with the project's overall goal, its activities, milestones, and key mission.

This deliverable stems from an update of the initial communication plan (D9.2), which was set up as a living document that was continuously updated, extended, refined, and adapted throughout the project's lifetime. It is also closely connected to the activities of T9.1 Dissemination and exploitation plan and monitoring and its Dissemination & Exploitation Plan (D9.1, updated in M18 as D9.6). In a close collaboration between TRI and SYNNO, both strategies have been aligned, ensuring maximum impact. Furthermore, the communication strategy is related to T9.3 Establish an online and media presence and the resulting D9.3 Press Kit (submitted in month 6 of the project). While D9.7 set out the overall strategy to promote the project and its activities, D9.3 reported on the variety of materials and tools set out in this communication plan. There is also a close relationship with WP8, in which the various guidelines and materials, as well as the bi-monthly reports, are created.

2 Update month 36: evaluation of the COVINFORM communication strategy

This deliverable, 'D9.11 - Final Outreach Report', outlines the learnings, best practices, and challenges in engaging with stakeholders in addressing emergency medical situations such as pandemics. An evaluation of the communication strategy so far has shown that the two most effective tools are the project website and the Twitter channel. As of September 2023, the project website has exceeded the KPIs of 12.000 unique visits. Among the social media channels, the Twitter channel has the most extensive reach, with approximately 300 to 1600 Tweet impressions per month with an average of approximately 600 Tweet impressions. It also reaches the broadest range of target groups: researchers and academia, other projects (in the same domain), and the general public. The engagement rate of the Twitter channel lies above 2,8 (reactions/impressions) for the last 90 days. The LinkedIn channel has a reach of approximately 200 viewers per post. The target group reached is primarily researchers &

academia. Since the Facebook channel generally did not have a high reach, it was shut down and replaced by an Instagram channel. On Instagram, we generated 131 followers within 17 months. The posts on Instagram get between 3 and 27 likes with an average of approximately 8 likes.

3 COVINFORM communication strategy

The communication strategy devised for COVINFORM is outlined in D9.2 Communication Plan (and in the updated version of the deliverable in M18 – D9.7 Communication Plan – Update M18). The communication activities and plan aimed to inform the media, the general public and the stakeholders of COVINFORM about the project and its results, as well as promote them and showcase the project's impact. The consortium made sure to capture the public's attention as well as to engage partner projects, researchers, NGOs, and policymakers working in emergency medicine through active social media channels and the creation of engaging material such as blogs, podcasts, and videos. Communication in the project has been greatly boosted by the fact that it focused on a high-profile topic that was widely covered. However, we have also faced a certain fatigue of the topic after more than two years into the pandemic. As such, COVINFORM tried to promote the project and its activities in engaging ways.

In order to develop a strategy that allows for fulfilling these goals, we tried to answer six key questions:

- WHY is the project important to the audiences and target groups? What are the communication objectives?
- WHO are the target audiences, and who will contribute content to which audience?
- WHAT are the key messages, and which content should be shared?
- WHERE will these messages and content be shared? Which channels and platforms will be used?
- HOW will we measure the impact and which formats and languages will be used for the target audiences?
- WHEN best to publish or communicate specific messages? How often?

These questions are addressed in the chapters below. Communication objectives

The key objectives of the communication plan were as follows:

- Provide widespread visibility to the project and its outputs.
- Develop a project brand and messages for each stakeholder group to create visibility and interest in the project's solutions, activities and results and thus target all stakeholders.
- Ensure that target audiences are convinced that due to COVINFORM more has been achieved than would otherwise be possible and as a result, the project has created measurable benefits to citizens and its stakeholders.
- Target key decision-makers who can support the implementation of the project.

- Demonstrate how the outcomes of COVINFORM are relevant to the lives of all citizens and how it is a vital project working toward the improvement of society as a whole.
- Ensure that the results of COVINFORM influence policymakers and other decision-makers around gender, emergency medicine, sociology, and other research disciplines.
- Participate in forthcoming EU Research Conferences and Workshops.

There is a partial overlap between the communication strategy and the dissemination and exploitation strategy (D9.1 Dissemination & Exploitation Plan; D9.6 Dissemination & Exploitation Plan – update M18). However, we have been careful to define the goals, target audiences and purposes of each activity as shown in the table below.

Table 1 Mapping between activities and their purpose

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Goal	Communicating the project and its results	Communicate the results and how they may be used	Making use of the results
Main target audiences	General audiences	Audiences that may use the results	Specific target groups which may uptake the results (policymakers, decision-makers, etc.)
Purpose of engagements	Show the benefit of the research	Facilitate the uptake of (scientific) results	Facilitate the uptake of all exploitable results

3.1 Target audiences

COVINFORM targeted the following audiences with its activities and intended outcomes:

- Decision-makers, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations, national planners and public authorities;
- Practitioners, healthcare workers, public health sector; public health authorities;
- Civil society, vulnerable individuals¹, citizen groups, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) & NGOs;
- Scientific community, researchers, academia;
- The general public.

Each of these audiences has been reached with customised messages. It is important to note that among our primary audiences, COVINFORM engaged with women, older people, persons with disabilities, individuals from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, migrants, Black and

¹ i.e., women, older people, persons with disabilities, individuals from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, migrants, BME groups, indigenous people, volunteers

Ethnic Minority (BAME) groups, indigenous people, volunteers, and the community of practitioners in its activities.

3.2 Key messages

COVINFORM has defined its key messages, as well as the channels of communication, in a way that guarantees that the different target audiences are provided with information relevant to them. The following table provides an overview of these.

Table 2 Target audiences, key messages & channels

Target audience	Key message	Key channels & activities
Decision-makers, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations, national planners and public authorities	COVINFORM is a research project that contributes relevant insights, especially lessons learned, and policy recommendations on a local, national and EU level to improve pandemic response. The project's focus on vulnerable and marginalised groups aims to ensure that future pandemic responses (to COVID-19 and/or other pandemics) will consider these groups accordingly. COVINFORM produces relevant information that allows decision-makers, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations, national planners and public authorities to design effective communication strategies leading to positive impacts on the extent and speed of behaviour change of individuals, groups and, communities within their respective social and cultural contexts.	Website, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials (particularly, flyer, whitepapers, policy briefs), webinars, workshops, demonstrations, bilateral meetings
Practitioners, healthcare workers, public health sector; public health authorities	COVINFORM examines public health systems, including long-term care infrastructures, to understand effects and impacts of the crisis, including those on vulnerable groups such as frontline healthcare workers. Using an intersectional approach, COVINFORM pays specific attention to women who are the majority of healthcare workers. The project aims to produce insights and activities particularly beneficial to women in such vulnerable positions. COVINFORM research outcomes are also relevant to decision-makers responsible for public health management and communication in pandemics, at a regional, national, EU, and international level.	Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials, webinars, journal articles, workshops, demonstrations
Civil society, vulnerable individuals, citizen	COVINFORM is a research project that identifies the impact that national, regional, and local COVID-19 responses have had on human behaviour, social dynamics, and physical and mental health within both general	Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication

Target audience	Key message	Key channels & activities
groups, CSOs & NGOs	populations as well as specific groups which have been impacted more severely due to a variety of social, economic and societal factors. The project examines the impact of physical distancing and lockdown measures in terms of social isolation and time spent indoors, as well as the disruption of work/school-life balance. To improve COVID-19, as well as further pandemic response, the project intends to collect input from civil society, (vulnerable) individuals and CSOs.	materials, research activities (interviews, focus groups, etc.), newspaper and magazine articles, face-to-face communication (virtual and physical)
Scientific community / researchers / academia	<p>COVINFORM as a research project contributes to the areas of interest and expertise (within and outside of the consortium), e.g., sociology, public health, emergency medicine, psychology, migration studies, anthropology, epidemiology, virology, gender studies, economics, risk communication, communication science & journalism, crisis management, ethical and societal impact assessment, political science, and human geographics.</p> <p>COVINFORM adds to the knowledge production in the above-mentioned fields by identifying strengths and weaknesses of current responses and communication strategies employed by national planners and healthcare decision-makers.</p> <p>The research in this project improves knowledge in the sector and is useful to researchers in the fields.</p>	Website, social media (especially Twitter, ResearchGate, LinkedIn), newsletter, printed materials, webinars, journal articles, workshops, conferences, demonstrations
Media and the general public	<p>COVINFORM is a research project that identifies the impact that national, regional, and local COVID-19 responses. It aims to understand the impact of measures such as lockdowns, social isolation, and physical distancing on human behaviour, social dynamics, and physical and mental health, as well as the impact on society as a whole. It will also tackle the multi-layered, societal problem of misinformation. COVINFORM identifies and analyses strategies for inclusive and effective COVID-19 communication as well as strategies to prevent misinformation, disinformation, malinformation, 'fake news' and conspiracy theories.</p>	Website, social media, newsletter, digital and printed communication materials, newspaper and magazine articles, face-to-face communication (virtual and physical), podcast

3.3 Principles

3.3.1 Non-discrimination

COVINFORM partners promoted the project and communicated its outcomes in a way that is free from discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion, or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age, or sexual orientation. Materials and content were created in a gender-inclusive and diversity-friendly way. This includes the selection of images for promotion materials, the overall image language of the project, as well as written texts.

3.3.2 Accessibility

COVINFORM took care to design all its (online) communication in a way that is accessible and barrier-free to people with disabilities. Images were published with alternative text to ensure the project website is screen-reader friendly, and we refrained from using colour as the only visual means of conveying information, following common guidelines on accessibility.²

3.3.3 Online-first approach

For all its promotional material, COVINFORM followed an online-first approach, thus reducing its ecological footprint. Material was only printed if necessary, for effective and impactful communication.

3.4 Instruments & methods

COVINFORM applied both personal, two-way and one-way communication, as recommended in the H2020 Communication guideline (European Commission 2014). The following tables describe the different tools, as well as their advantages and disadvantages for promoting the COVINFORM project.

Table 3 Communication methods: two-way communication

Interpersonal, two-way communication	Pros	Cons
Dialogues, face-to-face communication, bilateral meetings	Direct & immediate feedback, knowledge exchange	Time-consuming
Group discussions	Direct & immediate feedback, knowledge exchange	Difficult to arrange depending on the stakeholders/target groups
Conferences	Larger audiences of a particular (scientific) community, feedback-gathering & knowledge exchange, extend existing networks	Difficult to organise, possibly costly (both attending and organising)

² See e.g., <https://medium.com/salesforce-ux/7-things-every-designer-needs-to-know-about-accessibility-64f105f0881b>

Interpersonal, two-way communication	Pros	Cons
Brokerage events	Direct & immediate feedback from specific stakeholders, knowledge exchange, networking	Costly, time-consuming
Round tables	Good way to collect feedback and exchange knowledge, ideas	Difficult to arrange depending on the stakeholders/target groups
Exhibitions, open days	Engaging way to present project outcomes, potential to create high impact	Difficult to arrange and design, time-consuming and possibly costly, difficult to attract audience
Meetings	Good way to collect feedback and exchange knowledge, ideas	Difficult to arrange depending on number of participants, time-consuming
Workshops & seminars	Good way to collect feedback and exchange knowledge, ideas	Difficult to arrange depending on the stakeholders/target groups, time-consuming
Demonstrations & prototypes	Engagement with the intended users, interactive and hands-on feedback-gathering	Technical difficulties may lead to bad publicity if presented too early
Internet debates & social media	Engagement with different audiences, feedback-gathering, low costs, interactive	Misunderstandings may occur that lead to bad publicity of the project, trolls, time-consuming
Webinars	Engagement with specific audiences, possibility to gain feedback, discussions	Advertisement needed to gain audiences
<p><i>Smaller audience, lower costs, more efforts</i></p> <p><i>Interactive, good for acquiring input</i></p> <p><i>Flexible (easy to change tone, strategy & content)</i></p>		

Table 4 Communication methods: one-way communication

Mass media, one-way communication	Pros	Cons
Newspapers & magazines	Large audience, potential of high impact, credibility of mass media	Possibility of shortening the message and (unintentionally) changing it,

Mass media, one-way communication	Pros	Cons
		which may lead to misunderstandings
Press releases	Potential to gain the interest of mass media, decision-makers, policymakers	Limited engagement with the audience
Newsletters	Wide reach to an interested audience	Limited engagement with the audience
Manuals	Guidance and information	No engagement with the target audiences, needs clear and precise language, design issues
Brochures, booklets, flyers	Fast communication, potential to reach a large audience	Limited engagement with the audience
Videos	Raising awareness on the project and its topics, potentially reaching a broad demographic	Time-consuming and costly, not searchable, accessibility problems
Posters	Reusable, creative way to communicate results, visually attractive (if designed right), reaching a broad audience in limited time	Design is key to attract attention, need to select and reduce what can be communicated, which can lead to misunderstandings
Stickers	Fast and easy way to promote the project	No engagement with the target audiences
Website	Structured overview of a variety of information, possibility to provide information for download, potentially large audience	No engagement with the target audiences
Podcasts	Raising awareness of the project and its topics, potentially reaching a broad demographic	Limited engagement with the audience, time-consuming, not searchable, accessibility problems
<i>Potentially large audience</i> <i>Uses the credibility of mass media</i>		

From this pool of methods, those chosen for COVINFORM are introduced below. As indicated above, we used a mix of communication channels to address the different target audiences.

Importantly, the formats and channels chosen to communicate the COVINFORM project had to be adapted to the purpose of the communication and the audience it was directed at.

Figure 2 COVINFORM logo, fonts & colour sheet

Figure 3 Logo

Due to the multi-layered topic within COVINFORM, SYNYO designed a key visual language, as can be seen in the figure below. This helps to avoid a picture language that may contribute to stereotyping and exclusion of the different topics brought together within the project.

Figure 4 Key visual language

Figure 5 Leaflet/project factsheet

Figure 6 Stickers

Figure 7 Business cards

A project identity kit has been designed to provide an overview of the different materials and designs. The full identity kit can be found in the Annex.

3.4.2 Press releases

Over the course of the project, COVINFORM issued several press releases whenever a noteworthy event occurred. A first press release was issued at the project start, announcing the project and its aims. SYNYO and TRI wrote a general announcement, which partners could use, translate (if necessary), and distribute via their channels.

After the achievement of crucial milestones and other important moments in the project, the whole consortium and in particular members responsible for or participating in those tasks were asked to issue press releases. Press releases were published on the project website, as

well as on the respective partners' own (media) channels. They were also published via CORDIS Wire, and printed, if necessary and possible.

The COVINFORM press releases were targeted at a broad audience, from decision- and policymakers to public health experts to the general public. As such, they were written in a language accessible to all groups and avoided scientific terms.

Update M36

COVINFORM published the following press releases throughout the project:

- Launching COVINFORM, a project analysing the impact of COVID-19 governmental response on vulnerable groups ([available online](#));
- COVINFORM joined forces with its sister projects to increase impact in mitigating the risks of the COVID-19 pandemic ([available online](#));
- The Need for Inclusive Communication in Crisis – Findings From European Commission Funded Research ([available online](#)).
- New research has revealed how members of minority ethnic groups in South Wales coped with challenges presented by the Covid pandemic ([available online](#)).
- The COVINFORM project says thank you: a review (link unavailable as press release is to still to go live)

3.4.3 Print/online media

Print media include newspapers and magazines; they are an important tool to reach the general audience and vulnerable groups. Contrary to scientific journals, newspapers and magazines provide a more accessible form of communicating project results. COVINFORM aimed to leverage both printed and online newspapers and magazines on an international, national, and regional level, in order to reach different audiences in an integrated approach, combining a variety of channels, to increase the impact of communication activities.

Update M36

The HORIZON Magazine featured one article on vulnerable groups that quotes COVINFORM researchers from the University of Antwerp: How vulnerable groups were left behind in pandemic response. The article is [available online](#). While not at the centre of the COVINFORM communication strategy thus far, articles in print or online media are an effective way to reach the general public.

3.4.4 Scientific publications

As reported in D9.1 and D9.7, COVINFORM partners collectively aimed to publish a minimum of ten articles based on the project's key insights and results. Tailored to reach a specific audience, the scientific community, publications contributed to advancing the state of the art in the different disciplines represented in the inter- and transdisciplinary project. While the focus was put on peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings, the partners also sought to publish in other publication formats (e.g., edited volumes), and contribute posters and/or presentations at conferences.

Update M36

By the end of the project (M36), the below-mentioned journal articles and book were published or are under review and preparation.

Anson, S., Wieltschnig, P., Taylor, M., & Aspell, N. (2021) Understanding vulnerability to inform two-way inclusive COVID-19 communication. *medien &*, 49.

Anson, S., Bertel, D., & Edwards, J. (2021). Inclusive communication to influence behaviour change during the COVID-19 pandemic: examining intersecting vulnerabilities. In *COVID-19: Systemic risk and resilience* (pp. 213-234). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Miri, A., & Van Praag, L. (2021). Gender en migratie in tijden van pandemie. In L. Beeckmans, S. Oosterlynck, & E. Corijn (Eds.), *De stad beter na Corona? Reflecties over een gezondere en meer rechtvaardige stad*

Cerqua, A., Di Stefano, R., Letta, M., & Miccoli, S. (2021). Local mortality estimates during the COVID-19 pandemic in Italy. *Journal of Population Economics*, 34(4), 1189-1217.

Beljaars, D., & Shubin, S. (2022). Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot. Survey report for the Swansea Bay University Health Board. COVINFORM H2020 Project No. 101016247.

Molenaar, J., & Van Praag, L. (2022). Migrants as 'vulnerable groups' in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature. *SSM-Qualitative Research in Health*, 2, 100076.

Bertel, D., Johansson, B., Adler, V., & Ghersetti, M. (2023). Meme-Ing Accountability: Visual Communication as Character Assassination of Austrian and Swedish Politicians and Government Agencies During the COVID-19 Pandemic. In *Pandemic Communication* (pp. 117-140). Routledge.

Ghersetti, M., Ólafsson, J. G., & Ólafsdóttir, S. (2023). Watchdogs and government megaphones: The dual democratic roles of the news media during the Covid-19 pandemic in Iceland and Sweden.

Beljaars, D., Shubin, S., & Hassan, R. Opinions on Test, Trace, Protect and COVID-19 vaccination services by BAME and White people in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot. *Ethnicity*, 75(3), 17-21.

Molenaar, J., Robinson, H., & Van Praag, L. (2023). "A beacon of hope": a qualitative study on migrants' mental health needs and community-based organisations' responses during the COVID-19 pandemic in Antwerp, Belgium.

Manuel Tamayo, Isabel Bazaga, Rut Bermejo (2023) *Evaluación de la gestión de la pandemia COVID-19 en España*. Tirant lo Blanc

Anson, S., Adler, V. et al. - Addressing COVID-19 misinformation and inequalities through communication: Insights from COVINFORM and the WHO Regional Office for Europe, in: Troullinou, P., Bertel, D. & Loukas, G eds., *News consumption in the time of infodemic; human and societal factors of misinformation spread and socio-technical solutions*, Open Access Publisher (in press).

Ventre, Carla; Ambrosetti, Elena (2024) Migrant women population during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Rivista Italiana di Economia, Demografia e Statistica* (accepted).

Irene Sánchez-Vítores, Sara Carrasco-Granger, Javier Lorente (2023) Overcoming vulnerability: resilience strategies amongst migrants in Madrid during the COVID-19 pandemic (book chapter, accepted for publication).

Bengt Johansson, Sofia Johansson, Marina Ghersetti (2023) Information seeking and repertoires in migrant dense Swedish suburbs during the COVID-19 pandemic, in Risk and Crisis Communication in Europe: Towards Integrating Theory and Practice in Unstable and Turbulent Times (in press)

Robinson, Hannah; Van Praag, Lore; Molenaar, Jil. Feeling stuck: The micro-politics of migrant dwelling practices during COVID-19 in Antwerp. *Urban Studies*. (in review)

Boni, Z., Bertel, D., Adler, V. (2024) To Stay or not to Stay at Home? The Unintended Consequences of Public Health Advice for Older Adults in the context of Covid-19 and Urban Heat. *Social Science and Medicine*. (in review)

3.4.5 Policy recommendations & whitepapers

The COVINFORM project set out to publish four whitepapers and policy recommendations for decision- and policymakers. The whitepapers aimed to build on the insights of WPs 4-7, focusing on recommendations on government, public health and community response, as well as inclusive communication and combatting misinformation.

Update M36

White papers, policy briefs and factsheets produced as part of WP8.

At present, the COVINFORM project has produced three whitepapers and 11 policy briefs.

There are a number of additional white papers and policy briefs due to be published before the project comes to an end on 31 October 2023. These include:

Policy briefs

- 1) Addressing Vulnerability and Promoting Resilience in Social-Ecological Systems: A case study comparative analysis of the COVID-19 Pandemic throughout Europe (Beatriz Rosa (FS), Benjamin Trump (FS), José Palma-Oliveira (FS), Igor Linkov (FS)).
- 2) Healthcare policies during the pandemic: Preventing the spread of COVID-19 or inequality? (Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin (SU)).
- 3) Community mental health responses for migrants to deal with the COVID-19 pandemic in Antwerp.
- 4) The impact of COVID-19 on marginalized groups in Greece (Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA), Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA) & Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA)).
- 5) COVID-19 Governmental responses and challenges: The case study of low socio-economic status citizens in Greece (Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA), Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA) & Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA))
- 6) STRUCTURES, INSTITUTIONS AND ACTORS IN THE RESPONSE TO THE COVID-19 CRISIS IN SPAIN: Challenges, dilemmas and proposals (Javier Lorente, Manuel Tamayo, Isabel

Bazaga, Irene Sánchez-Vítóres, José Luis Postigo, Antonio Rodríguez. Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, España.)

- 7) ESTRUCTURAS, INSTITUCIONES Y ACTORES ANTE LA RESPUESTA A LA CRISIS DE LA COVID-19 EN ESPAÑA: Retos, disyuntivas y propuestas (Javier Lorente, Manuel Tamayo, Isabel Bazaga, Irene Sánchez-Vítóres, José Luis Postigo, Antonio Rodríguez. Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, España.)
- 8) Healthcare workers during the pandemic: lesson learned and the way ahead (Daniela Foresta, Elena Ambrosetti)
- 9) Policing during COVID-19: The impact of Coronavirus on Law Enforcement Agents (Ioannis Bagkatzounis (KEMEA) Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA) Anna Tsekoura (KEMEA))
- 10) Micro-politics of agency taken by residents living in Antwerp's as a consequence of COVID-19 (Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar & Lore Van Praag University of Antwerp)
- 11) "Community" in times of crisis: Perceptions of low-SES women in 10 EU countries (WORKING TITLE) (Isabella Tautscher and James Edwards (SINUS))

Whitepapers

- 1) INCLUSIVE COMMUNICATION IN TIMES OF CRISIS: lessons learned and recommendations from COVID-19 and other CBRNe incidents based on recent COVINFORM & PROACTIVE findings Anson, S., Bertel, D., Havârneanu G., & Petersen, L. (TRI & SYNNO)
- 2) White paper on public health responses during the COVID-19 pandemic: lessons learnt and recommendations for policy makers (Robinson H., Van Caudenberg R. & Van Praag L.)
- 3) Leveraging Public Momentum During a Crisis: Recommendations for Policy and Practice (Isabella Tautscher and James Edwards (SINUS))

Factsheets

- 4) Factsheet 01 – Workshop for responders. (MDA & SAMUR)
- 5) Factsheet 02 – Emerging vulnerabilities during the COVID-19 pandemic. (UniAntwerp)
- 6) Factsheet 03 – Effective and inclusive crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic lessons learnt. (SYNNO)
- 7) Factsheet 04 – Pandemic communication. How can we reach the most vulnerable. (AUTRC)
- 8) Factsheet 04 (DE) – Pandemie Kommunikation. Wie erreichen wir vulnerable Gruppen. (AUTRC)
- 9) Factsheet 05 – How to reach 'hard-to-reach communities' in the UK. (MDI)

Country reports

- 10) Country Report Wales – Communication Strategies during the COVID-19 Pandemic (SU)
- 11) Country Report Wales – Governmental Response (SU)

- 12) Country Report Wales – Public Health Response (SU)
- 13) Country Report Greece – Public Health Responses (KEMEA)
- 14) Pandemic Experiences of Minority Ethnic Groups in Swansea, Neath, and Port Talbot (SU)
- 15) Country Report Wales – Government responses to COVID-19 and vulnerability in Wales (SU)
- 16) Country Report Wales – Public health governance, preparedness, and vulnerability (SU)
- 17) Country Report Wales – Crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in Wales (SU)
- 18) Country Report Wales – The multiplicity of BAME migrant nurses’ vulnerabilities in South Wales (SU)
- 19) Country Report Wales – Vulnerability and Crisis The COVID-19 pandemic responses from civil society organizations in South Wales (SU)
- 20) Country Report Austria – Management and Responses of the Covid-19 Pandemic: Austria in Focus (SYNYO)

3.4.6 Promotional materials

The COVINFORM project produced a collection of promotional material throughout its lifetime. These included brochures, leaflets, factsheets, posters, stickers, as well as creative materials such as masks, bags, and others. These materials were a way to communicate the project in a direct and effortless way; they aimed to create familiarity with the project, its identity and (depending on the material) content, aims as well as objectives. As such, their main aim was to advertise the project in an easy yet understandable way to the whole range of target audiences.

All materials were published on the project website; wherever relevant, they were printed as well. SYNYO designed posters and other materials for partners for conferences or other events. Project partners were equipped with all relevant and necessary materials to circulate among participants of conferences, workshops, and other events and bilateral meetings.

Update M36

SYNYO designed flyers, pens, leaflets, and stickers, as well as business cards. These were distributed to the consortium to use to promote COVINFORM at events and were also made available on the project website: <https://www.covinform.eu/media/>

3.4.7 Videos

Videos were a way to present COVINFORM and its outcomes to all intended target audiences; they allow to communicate scientific outcomes and insights accessibly and understandably. A total of three videos were planned to be created and published during the project’s lifetime. These aimed to communicate key insights and outcomes in an accessible and interesting way. The videos were in line with the general visual identity of the project and communicated

crucial insights of the project. Videos were published on YouTube, embedded on the project website, and promoted via different channels, especially social media. Further information on the COVINFORM videos can be found [here](#).

Update M36

COVINFORM has produced two project videos (a detailed description of the videos can be found in D9.9 Videos – Update M30). The first COVINFORM video aims to highlight the project’s intersectional approach towards the analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic and discusses the different forces influencing its impact. The video starts with an introduction to the start of the pandemic and further stresses its unequal impact on communities and marginalised groups. Consequently, the theory of intersectionality is introduced and explained. Conclusively, COVINFORM's approach to the research of the pandemic is explained, emphasising the project's research and other activities.

The second COVINFORM video aims to showcase the experiences of different community groups of the COVID-19 pandemic, more specifically, the transmission of information about the pandemic and pandemic related topics, such as vaccinations.

The videos targeted our main communication audience – the general public. The video will act as a tool purposefully designed to attract the attention of the chosen audience and further raise awareness about the objectives of the COVINFORM project.

In addition to the project videos, COVINFORM has also published the recording of a joint webinar on “Vaccination refusal among healthcare workers”, co-organised with the NO-FEAR project, and two interviews, one on vaccinations in Israel and one on the Italian vaccine development.

Finally, the COVINFORM project produced five additional videos on community leads.

All COVINFORM videos can be watched on the project’s [YouTube channel](#); they have been promoted via social media. As entertaining and easily consumable content, project videos have been a successful part of the project’s communication strategy.

- Video 1 COVID-19 vaccination in Israel
- Video 2 COVINFORM & NO FEAR Joint Webinar
- Video 3 Italian vaccine development
- Video 4 Intersectionality and the COVID-19 pandemic
- Video 5 After two years of pandemic | COVINFORM Bi-monthly report #8, March 2022
- Video 6 After two years of pandemic | COVINFORM Bi-monthly report #9, May 2022
- Video 7 Community Voices
- Video 8 What is a community?
- Video 9 Shared location
- Video 10 Diversity
- Video 11 Joint Action

- Video 12 Sharing
- Video 13 Social Ties

3.4.8 Podcast & webinars

In addition to videos, the project set out to publish a podcast and organise or participate in webinars on relevant topics. Podcasts and webinars are a good way to communicate findings and create synergies with other research projects.

COVINFORM also organised its own webinars. Additionally, project partners were involved in the communication and dissemination of the project and its outcomes through third-party webinars. Similar to videos, podcasts will be promoted via the different channels available to the project.

Update M36

COVINFORM launched its podcast “Beyond numbers: COVID-19 and society”. A detailed description of the podcast, the process of making the podcast and an overview of each episode can be found in *D9.8 Podcasts – Update M28*.

The following podcast episodes were aired:

- E1: Intersectionality & Vulnerability
- E2: Communication & Public Health Campaigns
- E3: Data, Interpretation & Misinformation
- E4: Inequality - Gender, Mental Health & Migration
- E5: Community voices - Bringing it all together.

All episodes are embedded in the [website](#), available on Spotify, Apple Podcast and [RSS.com](https://www.rss.com).

COVINFORM partners organised and presented at the following webinars:

- How media and authorities handled the Corona crisis (M0)
- NO FEAR webinar on Human Resources management during COVID19 (M2)
- NO-FEAR webinar on risk communication (M2)
- NO FEAR webinar on Supply Chain Challenges during COVID 19 (M5)
- Minverva Lab Seminars: "COVID-19 and the overlap between job and home responsibilities: new evidence from the U.S. and Italy" (M5)
- Scandinavian Pandemic Response: Perspectives on Crisis Communication During the Pandemic in Nordic Countries (M5)
- NO FEAR webinar on COVID in children (M6)
- The impact of Covid-19 and community responses webinar organized (M6)
- NO-FEAR and COVINFORM joint webinar on vaccination hesitancy among healthcare workers (M7)
- Webinar for Dept. of occupational health science and psychology and for Academy for health and occupational life, University of Gävle. (M12)
- Invited presenter at webinar organized by CRISCOM (civil society organization) (M15)
- Webinar with Publicistklubben East (journalists' association) (M16)

- Public Health Network Cymru Webinar (M21)

These activities have been proven successful in engaging audiences and increasing the project's reach. As of M36, the podcast has achieved 1195 unique downloads.

3.5 Communication channels

COVINFORM made use of a variety of channels to reach out to its target audiences and stakeholders.

3.5.1 Project website

The COVINFORM website was developed in month 1 (November 2020) of the project and is available via <https://www.covinform.eu/>. It was the main communication tool of the project, and promoted the project and its results, in line with Grant Agreement Article 83.1.1 Obligation to promote the action and its results and Article 29.1 Obligation to disseminate results.

The main aim of the website was to inform relevant stakeholders, including decision-makers, policymakers, CSOs & NGOs, international organisations, national planners and public authorities, practitioners, healthcare workers, members of the public health sector, civil society, vulnerable individuals, citizen groups, the scientific community, and the general public about the COVINFORM project and provide relevant project-related materials and outcomes (such as publications and deliverables, but also project's logo, factsheets, etc.).

The project website was continuously managed, maintained and updated by SYNNO throughout the project's lifecycle. Visits to the website were monitored throughout the project's lifetime to keep track of the number of visitors and evaluate the effectiveness of dissemination.

Structure

Initially, the COVINFORM project website was structured into five main areas, as shown in the high-level sitemap of the website below (Figure 8). The main menu includes the main sections, i.e., the project overview, team, media centre, and contact. Marked in orange were subpages that had been implemented but not yet published in month 3.

Figure 8 Initial project website structure

Update M36

Over the course of the project, the COVINFORM website has been updated continuously. This also included an update of the initial structure, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 9 Updated project website structure

Initially, we expected that by M36, the COVINFORM website will have had 4,000 unique visits. As of month 18, the project website achieved 4,588 unique visits. Given the successful accomplishment of selected KPIs, the revisited *D9.6 Dissemination Exploitation Plan – update M18* set a new KPIs for M36. The new aim was to increase the unique website visits to at least 5500 by M36. At the end of the project (M36), the COVINFORM website had 22.466 unique visitors and 29.063 overall visits.

Home page

The home page provides a brief overview of the main objectives of the project, as well as all the partners' project logos. It also contains a banner inviting users to subscribe to the COVINFORM newsletter.

Blogs

This section contains blog posts by project partners. As initially defined in D9.1 and further updated in D9.6, partners contributed by writing blogs that were featured in the blog section of the website. Blog posts were actively promoted to the various stakeholder communities, e.g., via social media. This contributed to raising awareness about the project's results by increasing traffic on the website and enhancing opportunities for networking, forging collaborations and ultimately, exploitation.

Update M18

A blog schedule was created at the beginning of the project and was continuously updated in work package meetings. The blogs cover various topics, both the pandemic in general and the project's progress. The blog review process established by TRI and supported by SYNIO guaranteed cohesiveness between stylistic writing, good readability, and relevancy with the overall dissemination strategy of the COVINFORM project. As of month 36, a total of 42 blogs have been published; a list of the blog posts can be found in ANNEX II.

Project outputs

This section has been added since the initial communication plan was submitted. It provides an easy-to-grasp overview of the various project outputs. By the end of the project, this included the podcast, country reports, whitepapers, project videos, bi-monthly reports, and technical reports. Each of these outputs has its own sub-page. Since M18, the further sub-sections were added to reflect additional project outputs which have been created. These sections include scientific publications, policy briefs, and factsheets.

About Section

This section provides an overview of the main facts of the project. This includes the COVINFORM mission in a nutshell, the project's objectives, the methodology, the intended impacts, project facts (including the project number and duration), and the overall structure (i.e., an overview of the planned work in the work packages and tasks).

Consortium Section

This provides information on the partners of the project. As such, it included a description of the institutions and a link to the related institution's [website](#). A subpage introducing the Expert & Advisory Board was added in agreement with the experts, who provided their consent to feature a photo, relevant information and links to their home organisation. Furthermore, a page featuring COVINFORM's sister projects RESPOND, PERISCOPE, SHARE-COVID and RESISTIRE has been added; as well as a page to describe the PREparedness and

resPonse for emergency situAtions in euRopE (PREPARE) cluster of 13 H2020-funded projects on crisis management and preparedness.

Knowledge Repository Section

The Knowledge Repository integrates useful COVID-19 resources analysed as part of WPs 2-8. Planned to draw together the resources identified and evaluated as part of WPs 2-7, outputs of these WPs have been published continuously to build a knowledge repository of useful COVID-19 resources that are relevant for government and public health representatives, CSOs, NGOs, policymakers, and citizens. The COVINFORM COVID-19 Knowledge Repository has been launched in month 2 (December 2020) to deliver results from the very outset of the project.

Update M36

The Knowledge Repository has been extended into the WP2 Risk Assessment dashboard and COVINFORM website. The project outputs are available through various channels, including an existing repository on the COVINFORM website. To extend our reach, well-known online research libraries, such as [Zenodo](#), in addition to the EC platform, have also been exploited. Finally, the COVINFORM interactive dashboard provides functionality to combine data and resources about the COVID-19 pandemic, so that this experience can be used to inform the planning and management of future pandemic situations. It features resources designed to improve the wellbeing and mental health of the population, frontline workers, and members of vulnerable groups. The various libraries draw together COVID-19 resources that were identified as relevant for government and public health representatives, CSOs, NGOs, policymakers, and citizens. See section 2 *Dissemination plan* (Dissemination channels and tools – Project website) for further reference and updates.

Resources Section

The Resources section offers a media centre where dissemination materials are available for download, including the project logo in different formats, and press releases. It has been regularly updated and filled throughout the project's lifetime. The contents of the Press Kit (slide kit, infographic, and project summary) were included in the media centre. Furthermore, a subpage containing all newsletters also features.

Contact Section

The section shows the contact details of the coordinator (SYNYO GmbH) of this project. It provides a web form for getting in touch with the project team, and a link to the social media channels. For more information about the project or specific enquiries, a single point of access email is provided (office@covinform.eu).

Imprint & Privacy Statement

In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the website also contains a detailed privacy policy including information about the (tracking) cookies enabled on the website. Furthermore, an imprint is linked from the first page, providing contact details to the role of data processing and controller entity, i.e., SYNYO.

Further content

The updates foreseen in the previous version of the communication plan have been addressed and implemented on the project website.

Search engine optimisation

The website has installed an SEO plugin to support an increased visibility of the site. In addition, the website is connected with Google Webmaster Tools to increase the project index in search engines.

Google analytics

The project website is connected with the Google Analytics platform, which has helped us survey the usage of the site from end-users in different dimensions like location, language, device, technology, demographics, browser and more.

3.5.2 Newsletters & contact lists

A newsletter was set up via Moosend³ and a signup form was implemented on the website. The newsletter was sent out regularly, approximately every four months. This was a continuous action as part of task *9.2 Communication plan and monitoring*. The newsletter was produced by the partners; it contained items on pandemic response management and other topics covered by the project (e.g., wellbeing during the pandemic, means of countering misinformation).

The newsletter featured teasers and links to blogs written by project partners. Newsletters further promoted the bi-monthly reports produced by the partners. The COVINFORM newsletter also featured information about the activities in the Sister Projects and PREPARE cluster; furthermore, we contributed to these project's newsletters and thus maximised our reach. SYNYO was responsible for coordinating the newsletter contents, as well as its design.

An initial Moosend contact list was created on Moosend based on the project's stakeholder and media lists. The newsletters were thus sent to those who we believe may have a legitimate interest in receiving news about our project or stories related to pandemic management and the other topics covered by the project (for further information, see D9.6). The aim was to have 500 individuals/organisations signed up to receive the newsletter by M24 and a total of 600 by the end of the project in M36.

The newsletter signup form, which was implemented on the project website, was designed in accordance with the GDPR. Users using the sign-up form thus had to give their explicit consent. All newsletters were designed in a GDPR-friendly way, allowing the possibility to unsubscribe.

The newsletters were also published on the project website and on social media for wider dissemination.

³ <https://moosend.com/>

Update M36

As of month 36, the consortium has sent out nine newsletters, following the plan outlined in D9.2 and D9.7. By M36, there are 371 individuals subscribed to the COVINFORM newsletter. It did not meet the target KPI of 600 individuals/organisations subscribed to the newsletter. However, all newsletters are also available on the project website in a separate section. Moreover, we assessed that this tool for dissemination reached its capacity with the numbers that we achieved and therefore we increased our efforts for dissemination through other channels, like social media, events participation and presentations, and publications of bi-monthly reports, blog posts and other project outputs directly on our website.

3.5.3 Social media

COVINFORM intended to create an active social media presence on different social media platforms. The project has established a presence on [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [YouTube](#), and [ResearchGate](#). We posted about 2-3 times a week on Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook. The COVINFORM ResearchGate profile was updated whenever relevant outputs were available; similarly, videos were uploaded to the YouTube channel when available.

Twitter

As an initial communication channel aiming to increase the presence and visibility of COVINFORM, a Twitter page was created, available via https://twitter.com/COVINFORM_EU.

The Twitter page functions as an important communication tool throughout and beyond the project's lifetime, especially to reach out to the scientific community and communicate the progress of the project. Information about project activities were provided, as well as relevant information related to the COVINFORM project. The Twitter channel was used to display the project's outcomes: blog posts, bi-monthly reports or podcasts episodes were promoted to boost visibility and make the COVINFROM community aware. Besides the project's own output, articles, publications, or studies of interest published by newspapers, journals, and others, were shared via its channel to spread news and information about the still-ongoing pandemic, progress on vaccination, new measures, and other relevant development. The aim was not only to connect with the main players, institutions and scholars in this field for constant exchange as well as for cooperation on particular tasks, issues or questions; but also to keep up to date on all relevant news and scientific outcomes.

Besides the partners and their networks, relevant accounts were followed strategically, including all COVID-19-related research projects (from the first and second call for COVID-19 projects by the European Commission), and other relevant projects (e.g., on disaster resilience, misinformation, crisis communication, etc.). Relevant hashtags include, among others, #COVID19, #UnitedAgainstCoronavirus, #SafeVaccines, #VaccinesWork, #misinformation, #H2020 and #EUfunded. Furthermore, the hashtag #COVINFORM has been established in the project communication after checking that it is not used in other contexts. Partners have been encouraged to tag @COVINFORM_EU in any project-relevant tweets published from their accounts, e.g., when participating in events.

COVINFORM seek to collaborate with the official H2020 Twitter channels, encouraging them to share relevant research outcomes of the project. For example, a post has been tweeted by the REA account on 10 December 2020 on COVINFORM in the context of Human Rights Day 2020.

Update M36

The COVINFORM Twitter page has 468 followers; Twitter has thus been proven to be a successful channel. COVINFORM regularly interacted with its sister projects, as well as projects of the PREPARE cluster. Besides the regular content, social media campaigns have been created for the COVINFORM channels and disseminated through the Twitter page. In addition to campaigns created in 2021 and 2022, the COVINFORM project continued its yearly International Women's Day Campaign in 2023. The campaign focused on some of the research conducted as part of the project with women from low socio-economic status and their lived experiences of the pandemic.

Other social media channels

Other social media channels were also created as part of the project including:

- **LinkedIn:** to distribute project outcomes to further relevant stakeholders which helped to connect with stakeholders we could not reach via the newsletter. As of 26 October 2023, the LinkedIn account counts 256 connections and 287 followers. Similar content is published on LinkedIn as on the Twitter channel: project results, relevant articles, and studies, and of course, the COVINFORM campaigns. The reach and engagement rate on LinkedIn mirrors that of Twitter evenly, basically reaching slightly fewer people.
- **Facebook⁴:** to reach more stakeholders and communicate the project results to an even broader audience. As of October 2023, the Facebook page has 77 followers and 67 likes. The content posted via the Facebook channel is no different from the content posted on the other social media channels. However, it reaches only a minimal number of Facebook users and receives hardly any interaction (approx. one like/post). The Facebook page has been seen as an important channel to reach out to practitioners and practitioner organisations. However, due to the limited engagement, we are re-evaluating its usefulness and may replace it with a more suitable and engaging channel.
- **ResearchGate⁵:** here, the partners added relevant publications and other output relevant to the scientific community (such as the whitepaper or technical reports), reaching 260 reads by the end of the project.
- **YouTube channel⁶:** to upload project videos. Six videos with a total of 317 views have been uploaded.

⁴ available via <https://www.facebook.com/covinform>

⁵ available at <https://www.researchgate.net/project/COVINFORM-CORonavirus-Vulnerabilities-and-Information-dynamics-Research-and-Modelling-2>

⁶ available at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC2rwiA2bNVRs2tRPVszdaXA>

Update M36

Due to a low engagement on Facebook, we decided to discontinue our Facebook page and instead focus our energies on other social media channels: Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, and Research Gate. Key engagement numbers for the different social media channels are included below:

- **Instagram:** to reach more stakeholders and communicate the project results to an even broader audience. At the end of the project, we reached 131 followers. As such we exceeded the numbers of Facebook users and thus evaluate our decision to change social media channel as positive.
- **Twitter:** 468 followers
- **LinkedIn:** 256 connections and 287 followers
- **YouTube:** 638 views
- **Research Gate:** 260 reads

3.5.4 Stakeholder engagement & networking

The project leveraged both the partners' networks as well as the experts who expressed their support in a letter of support and formed the project's Expert & Advisory Board.

Expert & Advisory Board

An external Expert & Advisory Board (EAB) delivered valuable inputs at different stages of the project and contained experts who represented a broad variety of ecosystem actors. Through this board, COVINFORM was able to build direct linkages for research (e.g., for comprehensive stakeholder analysis and interviews) and further demonstration activities. Once travel restrictions allow face-to-face meetings, EAB meetings were connected with project meetings to build strong interconnections between all members of the project. Their input, advice and comments are considered and discussed by the whole consortium, thus contributing to the success of the project.

The table below gives an overview of EAB.

Table 5 Expert & Advisory Board members

Name	Affiliation
Maureen Fordham	Centre for Gender and Disaster, Institute for Risk and Disaster Reduction at University College London
Hendrik Olinder	Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency (MSB)
Stephen Drinkwater	Business School, University of Roehampton
Ellen Van Vooren	Children's Rights Knowledge Centre
Jane Farmer	Social Innovation Research Institute, Swinburne University of Technology
Uwe Kippnich	Coordinator Security Research at the Bavarian Red Cross

The EAB

- has been regularly informed about the project's development;
- regularly commented on the material produced during the project;
- offered input and advice to the project outputs;
- helped to disseminate the project results;
- served as intermediaries with other stakeholders and end users.

The last point is especially important since it highlights the fact that these partners played a crucial task in linking COVINFORM with important stakeholders. Furthermore, the EAB provided feedback and input to the created framework and material.

Update M36

EAB members have provided valuable input and support to the project throughout. For example, Maureen Fordham collaborated with COVINFORM members on a blog article⁷ in the context of the campaign for International Women's Day 2021. Uwe Kippnich supported COVINFORM member SINUS in Germany in the recruitment of research participants. Jane Farmer supported SYNNO in writing their conference procedure for the EASA Conference in 2022.

Partner networks

The project leveraged the partners' networks, aiming to maximise its impacts. While public outreach and engagement with existing projects and networks is part of T9.4, this section intends to provide guidance to partners to promote COVINFORM within their networks. Partners were invited to publish information about COVINFORM on their channels. Partners were asked to include at least one piece of information within their organisation's websites, including a link to the project's website.

For websites, blogs and other forms of longer written texts, any news item should have included at least:

- Project name and related contact information;
- Acknowledgement of the funding with the European Union emblem⁸: **This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.**

Wherever possible, the news item should also have included:

- The respective partner's role in the project;
- a description of the partner's contribution to the news item.

Partners were also asked to share relevant news items with the communication and dissemination leaders (SYNNO and TRI). A list of partner websites and newsletters is provided in ANNEX III.

⁷ Available at <https://www.covinform.eu/2021/03/08/why-gender-matters-in-the-covid-19-response/>

⁸ Reference document for EU logo: <https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/connecting-europe-facility/cef-energy/beneficiaries-info-point/publicity-guidelines-logos>

Sister projects & cluster events

A total of five projects have been funded under the H2020-SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2 topic. COVINFORM created synergies with the respective projects, PERISCOPE, RESPOND, SHARE-COVID, and RESISTIRE, as part of *T9.4 Public outreach and engagement with existing projects and networks* under the lead of TRI. A first cluster event was organised by the European Commission on 22 January, introducing the projects and their respective goals and activities.

Update M36

Since the beginning of the project, the COVINFORM consortium has been active in reaching out and establishing relationships with projects related to similar topics such as those addressed by COVINFORM. TRI has organised two successful sister project workshops. Moreover, a final conference was organised jointly by the sister projects in Brussels on 7 September 2023 to showcase the common themes that emerged from individual projects and discuss how to promote preparedness for future pandemics.

3.5.5 Events & presentations

One of the most efficient ways of communicating the activities and objectives of the COVINFORM project and disseminating its outcomes are events such as scientific conferences, exhibitions, workshops, and other events at the national and European levels. At such events, communication can be controlled and targeted specifically towards the audience, thus achieving high-impact communication. At the same time, such events offer bidirectional information exchange, as well as bilateral exchanges, and interactions with the industrial and scientific community.

Depending on the event, COVINFORM partners communicated the project's overall aims, specific outcomes or goals, or specific topics within the wider context (e.g., data modelling, misinformation). A list of relevant conferences is provided in D9.6. Consortium partners were aiming to attend at least one conference, workshop, and networking activities per partner (two per research partner) with pertinent EU and national projects.

Update M36

Project partners have participated in several events such as workshops, conferences, and other events. The list in ANNEX IV provides an overview of these events.

3.5.6 Channels of the European Commission

COVINFORM made use of the European Commission's channels, which provide an effective and powerful way to communicate the project, to spread project news and its results. These include:

- **CORDIS**, the Community Research and Development Information Service of the European Commission brings research results to professionals in the field to foster open science. <https://cordis.europa.eu/news/en>

- **Horizon Magazine**, the EU’s research and innovation magazine. <https://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- **Success stories**, most recent success stories from EU-funded Research and Innovation. https://ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/fp_en.cfm
- **research*eu**, the EC’s regular magazine which highlights the most promising project outcomes in a range of domains, with a focus on a particular theme in every issue. <https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu>
- **H2020 news**, providing articles about H2020 research projects. <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551>
- **Futuris**, providing the latest news about the leading scientific and technological research projects in Europe. <https://www.euronews.com/programs/futuris>

3.6 Communication phases

In order to achieve the desired impact of its communication, each step needs to be planned and timed carefully. Strategic planning of communication activities means thinking about the right time to send out a specific message to a specific target audience. Our communication timeline followed the project plan and key milestones that highlight important events of the COVINFORM projects, accompanied by major research insights.

Figure 10 Communication timeline

4 Monitoring

Throughout the project, like the project’s dissemination activities, communication was monitored to evaluate its effectiveness and impact. As part of D9.1, TRI developed a monitoring tool (see D9.1, Annex 2) for each partner to complete on a monthly basis, and especially during the reporting periods. The tool consists of an Excel spreadsheet in which the partners were to specify the details of the dissemination and communication actions

performed and the obtained impact (i.e., audience reached with each activity). All consortium partners were encouraged to keep track of each dissemination activity (and the audience reached whenever possible) as they took place using the provided monitoring spreadsheet. For full details, see D9.1, p. 23-24.

4.1 KPIs

The table below shows the KPIs defined for communication activities of COVINFORM partners and the status at M36.

Table 6 Communication targets and M36 update

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
Project website, Google analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 4.000 unique visits until M36 (initial) 5500 unique visits until M36 (updated) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All stakeholders Interactive and informative impact on interested audiences 	4,588 unique visits	22,466 unique visits
Project identity (logo, colour scheme, templates)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Logo & templates finalised until month 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All stakeholders Interactive and informative impact on interested audiences, ensuring the project has a recognisable brand identity 	Logo & templates finalised in month 1	Logo & templates finalised in month 1
Brochures & posters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First brochure and poster until month 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All stakeholders Interactive and informative impact on interested audiences, ensuring the project has a recognisable brand identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 project flyer and 1 infographic published 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 project flyer and 1 infographic published
Press releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 press releases published 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizens Researchers & academia, media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 press releases published & 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 press releases published

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distributed on CORDIS Wire (discontinued) 	<p>(including CORDIS Wire)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations ▪ Wide dissemination and communication of results, especially to the public. In particular to highlight a milestone in the project as well as to disseminate key outputs of the project 	distributed on CORDIS Wire	
Newsletters	Building a mailing list of 500 individuals/ organisations signed up to receive newsletters by M24 and at least 600 total by M36.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Citizens ▪ Researchers & academia, media (including CORDIS Wire) ▪ Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations ▪ Provide information about the project, its deliverables, recommendations and relevant news items (including links to other 	Four newsletter issues have been sent to the mailing list, which currently has 330 subscribers.	Nine newsletter issues have been sent to the mailing list, which has 371 subscribers. The newsletter is also available on the website

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
		dissemination and communication channels)		
Project factsheet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publication of flyer on website with 250 downloads ▪ 1.500 copies distributed at third-party events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All stakeholders ▪ Provides stakeholders with a brief introduction to the project and where to go for more information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 186 page views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 392downloads ▪ 1700 copies distributed at third-party events
Face-to-face / virtual meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engaging with at least 100 stakeholders from at least 6 different countries (not limited to the EU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Other projects ▪ Researchers & academia ▪ Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations ▪ Provision of information to and gathering feedback from stakeholders; engaging them and influencing the outcomes of the project and the future directions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ So far, COVINFORM engaged with more than 240 stakeholders from the scientific community by organising workshops 	<p>Through organization of workshops and webinars, and presentations and participation in conferences and other events, COVINFORM has engaged more than 6000 people, of which more than 5000 from the scientific community through conference attendances and presentations, 150 representatives the of civil society, more than 400 policy makers, and more than 400 medical</p>

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
				practitioners and first responders
Presentation at third-party events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At least 1 per partner (at least 2 for research partners) ▪ Communicating results via different channels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Other projects ▪ Researchers & academia ▪ Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations ▪ Academic and research partners in the consortium will use their contacts and will distribute and present the project's results during international seminars, conferences and meetings to enlarge the impact of COVINFORM 	At least 6 partners have attended external conferences.	28 conference presentations at 25 conferences, 10 conference attendances, and 38 workshop and other events participations. In some of these events more than one partner participated.
Peer-reviewed journal articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Submission & acceptance for publication of 10 articles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Other projects ▪ Researchers & academia ▪ Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations ▪ Provision of information about key issues raised by academics. 	Two publications written by COVINFORM partners have been submitted and accepted.	15 scientific publications (book chapters or journal articles) have so far been published or accepted. Two are currently under review.

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
		COVINFORM is committed to publishing the findings in leading open access international publications and thus, contributing to building research and knowledge in this area		
Blogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least once a month⁹ 10 blogs on third-party websites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other projects Researchers & academia Medical practitioners, policymakers, NGOs, international organisations Provision of information about key issues raised by academics 	So far, 24 blogs were published on the COVINFORM website.	42 blogs
Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of Twitter & LinkedIn¹⁰ followers: <100 – poor, 100-250 – good, 250+ - excellent 900 followers in total on social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All stakeholders (mostly citizens, other projects & researchers) Provides stakeholders with up-to-date information on the project and its outputs. Social media will facilitate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 368 Twitter followers 174 LinkedIn connections 81 Facebook followers 623 followers of social media in total 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 467 Twitter followers 287 LinkedIn followers 131 Instagram followers 883 followers of social

⁹ The consortium has agreed to start with monthly blog articles in the first phase of the project. Once the project has created first outputs, these numbers will be increased.

¹⁰ KPIs for further social media channels will be defined when channels will be launched.

Instrument	KPIs	Target audiences & impact	Status M18	Status M36
		communication with students, faculty members and academics and how they may benefit from COVINFORM's outputs and build on its acquired knowledge.		media in total
Online & offline campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 5 other projects and 10 other stakeholders involved in various online & offline campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All stakeholders Raised awareness of the project's results for research institutions. Highlighted the struggles of particular at-risk groups (e.g., gendered impacts of COVID and the rise of domestic violence) Encourage and promote respect for European values through our research findings. 	Campaigns for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Women's Day 2021 International Women's Day 2022 Partner Introductions Covid Words 	Campaigns for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Women's Day 2021 International Women's Day 2022 Partner Introductions Covid Words International Women's Day 2023

5 Lessons learnt from COVINFORM to apply to future pandemic-related projects

5.1 Engaging stakeholders in research (WP4,5,6,7)

Communication and outreach activities throughout the project have played a key role in supporting COVINFORM's research activities across Work Packages 4-7. Based on input's from project partners (SINUS, UANTWERPEN, FS and SU), this section highlights insights that can be

taken forward in future projects in relation to future research and policy, communication and dialogue, and stakeholder engagement.

Based on the research efforts and activities of WP4, leading to Deliverable D8.3, 'Guidance and recommendations for government and policy summary report' stakeholders, decision makers and policy experts have been furtherly and actively encouraged to conduct additional research and develop relevant policies, inspired by the main findings, lessons learned, and recommendations listed in D8.3. More specifically, the COVINFORM consortium has identified the following main issues and proceeded with the relevant, realistic, and feasible solutions:

- **Governmental Responses: impact, challenges, and critique:** Low SES citizens are struggling to make ends meet during COVID-19 due to the lack of accessible welfare policies. The welfare system during crises should be more comprehensive, as the absence of adequate governmental support can be a consequence of a long-standing social issue for single-parent families among low SES citizens. Non-pharmaceutical interventions such as movement restriction policies such as social isolation (lockdowns) and social distance measures may have a beneficial impact on the containment of the virus, nevertheless, they can have significantly negative impact on the economy of societies and wellbeing of low SES and vulnerable individuals if the implemented policies are prolonged, consecutive and a de-escalation – de-engagement strategy is absent. The negative impact stems from lack of social interaction, abrupt cease of employment as well as scarcity and/or unavailability of basic needs items and services.
- **Governmental Support: effective and ineffective measures:** A grassroots collection of opinions regarding desired support can yield valuable insights for policy development. Bureaucratic challenges can leave socio-economically vulnerable citizens stranded in times of need. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) can serve as an alternative approach to address systemic weaknesses.
- **Vulnerability:** Vulnerability is a complex issue magnified by COVID-19 and systemic deficiencies. The absence of welfare protocols may heighten the vulnerabilities of low SES citizens, while movement restriction policies can lead to unintended consequences such as deteriorating mental and physical health.
- **Governmental system mechanisms and relevant actors should develop protection mechanisms to address systemic grey areas and legislative weaknesses of the labour law,** which fails to protect employees who work on a remote basis. It is important to protect employee's labour rights by abuses that involve reduction of the wages of remote working employees, increasing workload and disrespect of set work hours, which likely lead to reductions of productivity. Remote and on-site employee rights should be monitored by suitable governmental agencies to avoid a cascading phenomenon of employee rights violation, even after the pandemic.
- **Government mechanisms should consider the employment challenges faced by low SES citizens, particularly single parents, among other low SES citizens, who may be the sole providers for their families. They should provide substantial materialistic support in the form**

of benefits and essential items, as well as psychological support if employment is suspended. Moreover, a post-pandemic socio-economic strategy should include a re-introduction to employment plan. This could involve governmental mechanisms partially covering the monthly wages of beneficiaries and encouraging business owners to employ them, potentially through tax incentives.

- It is recommended that actors who politicised and exploited the pandemic for personal gain, particularly by spreading falsified information should be held accountable. A post-pandemic perspective should be adopted to actively provide financial assistance for both vulnerable businesses, vulnerable citizens, and employees, reinforcing the healthcare system, and facilitate open dialogue to identify lessons learned, mistakes and how to improve responses for future crises as well as address the negative psychological impact that COVID-19 caused.
- It is recommended that a well-structured, clear, feasible preparedness and response strategy and a post-pandemic action plan that considers vulnerabilities of marginalised groups in order to mitigate the socio-economic consequences of the pandemic which were intensified pre-existing financial and social issues that posed a threat to their survival, is developed.
- It is important to facilitate open dialogue between the wider social structure, low socio-economic citizens, and the minority communities on bridging the gaps and identifying courses of action that can be beneficial for minority communities, particularly in relation to their socio-economic and psychological wellbeing.
- Decision makers should actively work on constructing a common framework between stakeholders such as authorities, scientific community, embassies, and administrative agencies at all governance levels, with emphasis on how to effectively communicate and implement measures relevant to the crisis at hand. Embassies should have a pivotal role in assisting foreign nationals, migrants, and refugees, particularly allowing them to overcome language barriers.
- Pre-existing lack of trust and misinformation may negatively impact policy and measure implementation authorities (i.e. law enforcement agents). Decision makers should take into consideration weaknesses of the civil protection responses, particularly in high criminal activity areas and reinforce citizen protection which will subsequently mend trust issues. Authorities should provide proper training and education, particularly to improve the social interaction skills of authorities, as well as adequate wages that compensate the risks of their daily duties and responsibilities of deployed authorities (i.e. law enforcement agents).
- Stakeholders and communication experts are recommended to take into account the importance of conducting communication activities (i.e. debates) based on open dialogue and opinion multi-polarity. The lack of multiple points of view on traditional media panels may have decreased their popularity among the general and minority populations.
- Communication campaigns should be clear and targeted, while also inclusive of specific socio-demographic groups, which may have been overlooked during COVID-19. Communication experts should employ a variety of means of communications during crises, whereas in relation to social media, could also employ the re-direct method which uses

targeted ads which can both inform social media end-users and more importantly, it can act as an effective method to actively combat disinformation. In relation to vaccination, experts should communicate the usefulness of the vaccine for both the general population and vulnerable populations (i.e. cancer patients), their function and potential side-effects in a clear and transparent manner.

Based on D8.3 and all the relevant work conducted within the context of WP4, the COVINFORM consortium actively engaged and encouraged decision makers, policy experts and relevant stakeholders, to conduct additional research and proceed with the development of relevant policies, inspired by the aforementioned main findings, recommendations and lessons learned.

The need to engage stakeholders in research (and policy making) was highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic, which was during the first phase immediately overlooked. Stakeholders can further reflect on different needs, give voice to people that take up a vulnerable position in society, and bring in expertise on how to deal with these needs. Furthermore, they can facilitate access to reach out to groups that are often not sufficiently reached by policy makers and other organisations. Finally, the inclusion of stakeholders further added to reflect on a wider variety of communication means and channels, challenging the existing research methods and communication channels used. These processes provided useful insights for researchers and should be considered when writing down research insights and reflecting upon researcher positionalities.

To engage stakeholders in research, some reflections need to be made on the power relations between the stakeholders and researchers, which is even more relevant during crisis situations. Existing preparedness plans are needed to streamline these collaborations and to support stakeholders when participating in research. This could for instance relate to financial resources, human resources but also to how such collaboration should look like. During the COVID-19 pandemic, additional burdens were placed on large groups of stakeholders, in the tasks they performed, the urgency, time, home-work balance and risks to catch and spread the COVID-19 virus. Engaging them in research did not reduce these burdens and resulted in additional stresses by many stakeholders. This often even reinforced existing gender, ethnic, racial and social inequalities, while the research objectives wanted to go against this.

One example of successful stakeholder involvement can be attributed to early alignment of the already very similar goals of Swansea University and the Swansea Bay University Health Board and regional Community Cohesion Officer. Using collected data by the stakeholder, the Swansea team determined the analysis and results development of a large survey. In turn, both stakeholders offered their network contacts for the COVINFORM project interviews. For the second survey study the Swansea team was asked to do by the Health Board, the Swansea team collaborated on all aspects of the study, including the research questions, the survey questions design, and performed the analysis and wrote the report. As the recruitment for one of the research elements for WP3 underperformed, that second survey research was used instead.

5.2 Engaging end-users (WP2)

T2.5 entailed an iterative evaluation of the COVINFORM dashboard by both external end-users and end-user groups within the consortium. The end-user groups engaged included public health practitioners and researchers, public health policymakers and civil society organisation decisionmakers, journalists and other communications professionals, and academic researchers in multiple disciplines. Four activities were conducted:

- Workshop 1 (May 2021): Online requirements elicitation workshop (N=5 internal and external end users)
- Workshop 2 (October 2022): In-person cognitive walkthrough workshop (N=13 internal end users)
- Workshop 3 (July 2023): Online cognitive walkthrough workshop (N=4 internal end users)

Final usability tests (September 2023): individual concurrent think-aloud interviews and quantitative data collection (N=12 external end users)

The cognitive walkthrough, which is based on the theory of facilitated learning by exploration in the field of human-computer interactions, was developed as a means of evaluating “walk-up-and-use” interfaces, i.e., interfaces that do not require special training (Lewis et al. 1990). It is a review process in which the developer of an interface presents the proposed design to a group of peers, including end-users, who evaluate the interface using task-based criteria (Wharton et al. 1994). The concurrent think-aloud interview is a well-established method of studying “task-based cognitive processes” in general, and human-computer interactions in particular (McDonald et al. 2012, pg. 3). The sequential combination of these two methods allowed for an iterative, user-oriented engagement and development cycle:

- User input was solicited during workshops;
- The dashboard was modified in response to user input;
- The usability of the end result was comprehensively tested, providing feedback for exploitation.

During the end phase of the project, the development team at TRI have made final improvements to the dashboard based on the usability testing, in preparation for the final review. Further consideration will be given to the comprehensive usability report (D2.5) during post-project exploitation activities.

5.3 Engaging with stakeholders in addressing medical situations (e.g., pandemics) (D3.8)

The work carried out in WP3, culminating in D3.8 (Final Case Study Reports and Comparative Report), required engagement with a broad spectrum of stakeholders. This encompassed those directly involved in crisis response, particularly within the medical field, as well as stakeholders profoundly impacted by the pandemic, such as vulnerable groups. This collaborative approach was fundamental to the development of the project’s case studies.

Moreover, the comprehensive analysis of these case studies yielded invaluable insights and innovative policy recommendations. It is hoped that these recommendations will assume a central role in future stakeholder engagement efforts concerning medical crises. Consequently, the aspects taken into consideration and lessons learnt regarding COVINFORM's stakeholder engagement processes offer valuable insights that can be effectively applied to upcoming projects related to pandemics and health crises.

To begin, it is crucial to recognize that traditional perceptions of risk communication often center on the delivery of messages aimed at persuading or involving the audience. This conventional approach assumes a persuasive process where the communicator endeavours to convince the audience of certain information that is communicated as an absolute truth. However, it's important to acknowledge that conventional strategies, focused on providing information and convincing stakeholders, have their limitations. Such strategies do not necessarily foster confidence, goodwill, or proactive engagement. In fact, they can sometimes elicit defensive responses. Furthermore, both risk communication and stakeholder engagement are embedded within a broader framework encompassing social, cognitive, and emotional factors that extend beyond conventional considerations. Stakeholders vary in their risk perceptions, and factors like perceived control and trust play vital roles in these processes. Moreover, stakeholders often harbour specific concerns that require attention, such as issues related to fairness, equity, trust, access, power-sharing, or the duration of engagement. For instance, people tend to be sceptical when confronted with scientific conclusions presented as unwavering "truths". However, they are receptive to scientific reasoning, where the focus lies on understanding the procedures leading to these conclusions collaboratively.

Thus, when engaging with stakeholders, it is imperative to actively involve them in the process, identify common objectives and give them control and accountability. The process should commence with a clear definition of the problem within its broader context. If the project involves any inherent risks, these should be assessed within their respective contexts. Potential risk management strategies should be explored, and decisions regarding which options to implement should be made collaboratively. Subsequent actions and evaluations of the outcomes should also occur in close collaboration with stakeholders. Moreover, the process should remain flexible, ready to adapt based on new information or developments that could alter the necessity or nature of risk management. This adaptability should be achieved through iterative cycles of communication and engagement with stakeholders.

More specifically, when engaging with stakeholders in addressing medical situations like pandemics, it is important to initiate stakeholder engagement at an early stage and maintain regular, open communication throughout the project to ensure that their insights and needs are considered from the project's beginning to its conclusion. To enhance comprehensiveness, a wide range of stakeholders should be involved, from healthcare professionals and policymakers to community leaders, affected populations and representatives from diverse sectors (e.g., public health, social services, education). It is good to encourage collaboration among stakeholders from different sectors to address multifaceted challenges since cross-sectoral coordination can lead to more effective responses. With a wide range of stakeholders,

collaborative decision-making processes should be implemented, as mentioned above; this way, stakeholders can feel empowered to contribute to project goals and actions and they are encouraged to have an active participation in shaping the response to medical crises.

Given the importance of establishing trust and giving control, the project should provide transparent and accessible communication channels and materials for stakeholders, as well as ensure that information is clear, accurate, and easily understood. In this sense, it is important to share relevant data and research findings with stakeholders promptly, fostering trust and enabling them to make informed decisions and recommendations. When there is opportunity, it is also crucial to engage stakeholders in the research processes, allowing them to contribute with their knowledge and experiences since this collaborative approach can lead to more effective interventions and policies. Fostering long-term relationships with stakeholders beyond the immediate crisis is also very encouraged, since maintaining these connections can help build resilience and preparedness for future health emergencies.

Furthermore, it is important to be culturally sensitive and aware of the characteristic needs and beliefs of different communities and local contexts when engaging with diverse stakeholders, which means tailoring communication and interventions having that in mind. Prioritize ethical considerations, including informed consent, data privacy, and respect for autonomy and human rights.

Finally, the ability to pivot and adjust to changing circumstances is crucial in dynamic situations like pandemics. Consequently, the project should be prepared to adapt strategies and interventions based on feedback and emerging needs. In this sense, it is also essential to acknowledge that not all strategies will succeed. Be willing to learn from failures, adapt, and refine the project's approach; this includes regularly evaluating the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement strategies and making necessary adjustments to enhance their impact.

Incorporating these lessons and recommendations can contribute to more inclusive, responsive, and effective approaches in future projects that involve engaging with stakeholders in addressing medical crises such as global pandemics.

5.4 Crisis management plan within EU-funded projects

In D9.2 Communications Plan, the COVINFORM project set out an outline of steps to take in light of a crisis situation. The plan delineated how to proceed before a crisis, during a crisis and after a crisis. Considering the volatile and ever-changing nature of a pandemic, compiling a detailed crisis management plan was useful to map out how to approach a crisis or particularly heightened moment within the context of a pandemic (for the COVINFORM crisis management plan see Annex V).

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has provided an update of the COVINFORM project's communication plan and a summary of all communication and outreach activities. More specifically, this deliverable has provided an overview of the activities undertaken to inform, engage, create awareness, and promote information about the project, its aims, funding sources, results, impacts and wider societal implications. Throughout the deliverable, the consortium has highlighted the strategic and targeted measures to inform the media and the general public about the project and its results as well as promote them and showcase the project's impact. The deliverable defines key messages to the project's target audiences and stakeholders and appropriate communication channels and instruments to communicate them, including newsletters, social media, and mass media.

7 References

Lewis, C., Polson, P., Wharton, C., & Rieman, J. (1990). Testing a walkthrough methodology for theory-based design of walk-up-and-use interfaces. *Proceedings of CHI 1990*: 235-242.

McDonald, S., Edwards, H.M., & Zhao, T. (2012). Exploring think-aloud methods in usability testing: An international survey. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication* 55(1): 2-19.

Wharton, C. Rieman, J., Lewis, C. and Polson, P. (1994) *The Cognitive Walkthrough Method: A Practitioner's Guide*. In J. Nielsen and R. Mack (eds.) *Usability Inspection Methods* (New York: Wiley) 105-140.

ANNEX I. Identity Kit

COVINFORM

Identity Kit

SYNYO GmbH

Version 1.0

Contents

Identity Overview

- Logo, Color Codes & Fonts

- Key Visual

Print Materials

- Leaflet / Factsheet

- Rollup

- Business / Contact Cards

- Sticker

Screen Design

- Social Media Banners

- Powerpoint Elements

Corporate Design

Identity Overview

Logo and Colours

Picture Language

COVINFORM > Identity Kit

3

Identity Overview

Logo

Leaflet (A5)

Rollup (85x200cm)

Presentation Templates

Twitter Banners

Contact Cards (85x55)

Sticker

COVINFORM > Identity Kit

4

Logo

Logo, Colour Codes, Fonts

Logo

Logo Solid Black

Logo Solid White

Clearspace

RGB 255/148/66
HEX #FF9442
CMYK 0/51/81/0

RGB 255/187/134
HEX #FFBB86
CMYK 0/31/50/0

RGB 255/255/201
HEX #FFE1C9
CMYK 0/13/19/0

RGB 72/186/189
HEX #48BADD
CMYK 66/3/29/0

RGB 0/141/141
HEX #008D8D
CMYK 59/59/55/18

RGB 0/109/107
HEX #006D6B
CMYK 89/59/55/18

TW Cen MT Bold 123456789#!?!"

TW Cen MT Regular 123456798#!?!"

Headline Font (Google free font alternative)

Source Sans Pro Light 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Light Italic 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Regular 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Italic 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Semibold 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Semibold Italic 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Bold 1234567890#!?!"

Source Sans Pro Bold Italic 1234567890#!?!"

Body Font (Google Free Font)

Key Visual instead of Picture Language

Print Materials

Leaflet

Rollup

Business / Contact Cards

Folder

Sticker

COVINFORM › Identity Kit

7

Leaflet

A5

COVINFORM › Identity Kit

8

Leaflet Backpage

A5

PROJECT BACKGROUND
L'associació d'informació d'eventos, modelant i analitzant d'elles, veu el seu objectiu principal proporcionar informació de qualitat i de manera accessible a les persones que ho necessiten. Per això, el projecte COVINFORM té com a objectiu principal proporcionar informació de qualitat i de manera accessible a les persones que ho necessiten. Per això, el projecte COVINFORM té com a objectiu principal proporcionar informació de qualitat i de manera accessible a les persones que ho necessiten.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES
El projecte COVINFORM té com a objectiu principal proporcionar informació de qualitat i de manera accessible a les persones que ho necessiten. Per això, el projecte COVINFORM té com a objectiu principal proporcionar informació de qualitat i de manera accessible a les persones que ho necessiten.

PROJECT FACTS
Dates: 01.11.2020 - 31.10.2023
Programa: H2020
Grant No.: 101019166
Coordinator: SWIO

FOLLOW US & FIND OUT MORE ABOUT OUR LATEST DEVELOPMENTS
@covinform

CONTACT US
www.covinform.eu
info@covinform.eu
@covinform

Logos of partner organizations at the bottom.

Leaflet A5

Rollups

Draft

COVINFORM

Coronavirus Vulnerabilities and Information dynamics Research and Modelling

www.covinform.eu
info@covinform.eu
@covinform

Logos of partner organizations at the bottom.

Rollup 85 x 200 cm

Business Cards

85x55 mm

Sticker

100x30 mm

50x50 mm

Screen Design

Social-Media Banners Powerpoint Elements

Social Media Banners

Existing for Twitter, Facebook, Youtube, LinkedIn

Twitter Header 1500 x 500 px

Twitter Profile Image 400 x 400 px

Twitter Posts (1024x512)

Presentation Elements

COVINFORM

Coronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFORMATION dynamics Research and Modelling

xyz Conference
John Doe | Head of Research

Vienna | example venue 17
05.11.2020

Agenda

Masterformat bearbeiten

Time	Description	Partner
09:00 – 11:00	Headline xxxxxx	PartnerAcronym
09:00 – 11:00	Headline xxxxxx	

COVINFORM 7

Titel hinzufügen

Masterformat bearbeiten

- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx

- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx

- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx
- xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx

Open Tasks

COVINFORM 14

Presentation Elements

RGB 255 / 148 / 66
HEX #FF9442
CMYK 0 / 51 / 81 / 0

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HEX #48BABD
CMYK 66 / 3 / 29 / 0

RGB 255 / 187 / 134
HEX #FFBB86
CMYK 0 / 31 / 50 / 0

RGB 0 / 141 / 141
HEX #008D8D
CMYK 84 / 25 / 46 / 3

RGB 255 / 255 / 201
HEX #FFE1C9
CMYK 0 / 13 / 19 / 0

RGB 0 / 109 / 107
HEX #006D6B
CMYK 89 / 39 / 55 / 18

ANNEX II. Blog posts

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
1	COVINFORM: Project on social, behavioural and mental health-related issues kicked off	SYNYO	24/11/2020
2	Understanding vulnerability through dialogue: two-way dialogue and inclusivity in COVID-19 communication	TRI	21/12/2020
3	First lessons learned from COVID-19 vaccination in Spain	SAMUR	22/01/2021
4	COVINFORM at the COVID-19 2C sister project meeting	TRI	01/02/2021
5	Quarantine – history repeated	SYNYO	22/02/2021
6	Why gender matters in the COVID-19 response	SYNYO & TRI	08/03/2021
7	The COVINFORM team – supporting gender equality in EU Research and Innovation	SYNYO & TRI	08/03/2021
8	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Romania handled the outbreak	SNCRR	17/03/2021
9	The COVAX Facility: the way forward to ensure equitable distribution of COVID-19 vaccines?	UANTWERPEN	01/04/2021
10	Tackling COVID-19: collaboration for better results	TRI	15/04/2021
11	Joining forces in mitigating risks of the COVID-19 pandemic	TRI	07/05/2021
12	What is the Pandemic Teaching? Vaccines in a changing economic and social context	SAPIENZA	27/05/2021
13	Timely, transparent, targeted? Government communications during the pandemic		21/06/2021
14	One size does not fit all – information seeking during the COVID-19 pandemic in a segregated society	UGOT	07/07/2021
15	Red Cross in the COVID-19 pandemic – how Austria handled the outbreak	AUTRC	02/08/2021
16	Government and the pandemic: structures and response	KEMEA	18/08/2021
17	18 months of COVID-19 pandemic in Germany	SINUS	10/09/2021
18	COVID-19 and mental health: a ‘tsunami’ of problems?	UANTWERPEN	06/10/2021
19	Pandemic mitigation for everyone: Ethnic differences in Wales	SU	23/11/2021
20	Generation COVID	SYNYO	10/12/2021

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
21	Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories	MDI	20/12/2021
22	“Can we at least freak out?” Memes and COVID-19	SAPIENZA	22/02/2022
23	Nobody told us what to expect (except health professionals and our own simulations)	FS	16/03/2022
24	Italy in lockdown: The ultra-secular battle of laughing to avoid crying	SAPIENZA	13/04/2022
25	"Un-masking the Mask-Issue": Examining People's Sense-Making Processes and Risk-Cultural Norms regarding Facemasks	UGOT	27/04/2022
26	Summer holidays 2022: may the COVID be with you (hopefully not)	URJC	19/08/2022
27	Monkeypox in the time of COVID-19: Are we on our way to a new pandemic?	TRI	30/08/2022
28	New crises, same resilience?	SINUS	18/10/2022
29	Has COVID-19 changed our cities? Urban planning following the pandemic	UANTWERPEN	28/10/2022
30	Compulsory vaccinations and skipping contact restrictions – differing narratives of freedom in the German middle class	SINUS	07/12/2022
31	Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?	TRI	18/12/2022
32	“Bridging the gap”: The importance of interpersonal risk and crisis communication	UGOT	31/01/2023
33	Let me explain: why we use intersectionality and complexity theories	FS	18/04/2023
34	How COVID-19 has exposed housing inequalities: insights from Antwerp	UANTWERPEN	21/06/2023
35	Policy and practice mismatches in governmental responses during the COVID-19 pandemic	KEMEA	26/07/2023
36	Delivering inclusive and accessible COVID-19 communication in Birmingham (UK)	TRI	17/08/2023
37	Understanding the Systems we Live in: Deconstructing the Systems we Live by	FS	28/09/2023
38	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 1	SINUS	20/10/2023
39	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part 2	SINUS	24/10/2023

Number	Topic	Partner	Published
40	The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part A	TRI	25/10/2023
41	The Challenges of Understanding Covid-Related Risk: Part B	TRI	27/10/2023
42	Three Years of COVINFORM: A little glimpse into what we have done	SYNYO	31/10/2023

ANNEX III. Partner websites & newsletters

Partner	Website & other relevant channels
SYNYO	Website: https://www.synyo.com/ Email: office@synyo.com
MDA	Website: https://www.mdais.org/en Twitter: https://twitter.com/mda_israel
SAMUR	Website: www.madrid.es/samur Twitter: https://twitter.com/SAMUR_PC LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/unicatt/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/SAMUR-Protecci%C3%B3n-Civil-535855803253673/
UCSC	Website : https://www.unicatt.it/ & https://www.policlinicogemelli.it/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/Unicatt & https://twitter.com/cattolica_news & https://twitter.com/ucsc_int LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/unicatt/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/unicatt YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC7cpma8tI8NkmVar9OvbQ_g
SINUS	Website: www.sinus-institut.de Email: info@sinus-institut.de & COVINFORM@sinus-institut.de LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/sinusinstitut Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/SINUSInstitut/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCozU8cHLJqn-IQvCfnvwFQg Xing: https://www.xing.com/companies/sinusmarkt-undsozialforschunggmbh
TRI	Website: https://www.trilateralresearch.com/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/TRIResearch LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/in/trilateral-research-7278b3135/
KEMEA	Website: http://kemea.gr/en/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/center-for-security-studies-kemea-/ instagram: https://www.instagram.com/kemea_athens/?hl=en
FS	Website: https://factorsocial.pt/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/factorsocialpt LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/10520744/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/factorsocial.pt
AUTRC	Website: www.rotekreuz.at Twitter: https://twitter.com/rotekreuzat

Partner	Website & other relevant channels
	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/austrian-red-cross Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/roteskreuzat/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/c/roteskreuz/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/roteskreuz_at/?hl=de TikTok: www.tiktok.com/@roteskreuz_at
MDI	Website: https://www.media-diversity.org & https://getthetrollsout.org/ Email: info@media-diversity.org Twitter: https://twitter.com/MDI_UK & https://twitter.com/GetTrollsOut LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/media-diversity-institute/about/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/media.diversity.institute & https://www.facebook.com/getthetrollsout YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/MediaDiversity/featured & https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCcbcqBE7O_qRIWQ8OyPUJXw Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mediadiversityinstitute
SNCRR	Website: www.crucearosie.ro Email: crr@crucearosie.ro Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/crucearosieromana Instagram: www.instagram.com/crucearosieromana
UANTWERPEN	Website: https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/ & https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research-groups/cemis/ Email: cemis@uantwerpen.be Twitter: https://twitter.com/UAntwerpen?ref_src=twsrc%5Egoogle%7Ctwcamp%5Eserp%7Ctwgr%5Eauthor LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-antwerp/mycompany/ & https://www.linkedin.com/company/uantwerpen-cemis/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/UAntwerpen & https://www.facebook.com/UACeMIS YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/UAntwerpen Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/uantwerpen/?hl=nl
SAPIENZA	Website: https://www.uniroma1.it/en/pagina-strutturale/home & https://web.uniroma1.it/memotef/en Email: comunicazione@uniroma1.it & stampa@uniroma1.it Twitter: https://twitter.com/sapienzaroma Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/SapienzaRoma/ YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/SapienzaRoma Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/sapienzaroma/

Partner	Website & other relevant channels
URJC	Website: www.urjc.es & www.goodgovernanceurjc.org Email: goodgovernanceurjc@gmail.com & joseluis.postigo@urjc.es Twitter: https://twitter.com/Governance_URJC
SU	Website: https://www.swansea.ac.uk/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/SwanseaUni
UGOT	Website: www.gu.se/jmg & www.gu.se Email: forskarkollegiet@jmg.gu.se & jmgalla@jmg.gu.se Twitter: https://twitter.com/JMGoteborg LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/3779443/ Facebook: www.facebook.com/JMG.GU YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vzSxIAO8t8Y&list=PLJdM8I9zGPNAEv1WznGZ8En5qvdrq5eNa

ANNEX IV. Overview of events

Conferences (Presented)	6th Society for Risk Analysis Europe Nordic Chapter conference: “Risk Analysis: from Perception to Prediction”	M1
	The Society for Risk Analysis - European Conference 2021	M8
	Gray Rhino, Black Swan or Elephant in the Room: The Role of Crisis Communications in disruptive events.	M12
	SRA 2021: Risk Science and the Policy Interface	M14
	American Association of Geographers Annual Meeting 2022	M17
	La calidad institucional como fundamento de la gestión eficaz y honesta del Plan Nacional de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia en el contexto Covid-19 - Institutional quality as a foundation for effective and honest management of the National Recovery, Transformation and Resilience Plan in the context of Covid-19	M19
	EASA2022: Transformation, Hope and the Commons	M21
	European Society for Health and Medical Sociology Conference	M22
	AISU 2022	M23
	5th Congress of the Portuguese Psychologists Association	M23
	Netwerksessie integratieonderzoek over de impact van de COVID-19-pandemie op personen van buitenlandse herkomst	M23
	Effects of integration on information seeking. Media use and information seeking among Swedes and immigrants during the COVID-19 pandemic.	M24
	European Public Health Conference 2022	M25
	AISP POPDAYS 2023	M28
	American Association of Geographers Annual Meeting 2023	M29
	Population Association of America Annual Meeting	M30
	1st International Summit for Pandemic Management, STAMINA Project	M31
	Accessing healthcare in the EU: bridging gaps & tackling vulnerabilities	M31
	Dag van de Sociologie "Covid, gentrification and immigrant mental health "	M31
	LIX Scientific Meeting of the Italian Society of Economics Demography and Statistics	M31
SRA Europe 2022 Lund, Sweden. Palma-Oliveira & Antunes, In search of the Grall: what means an effective risk communication and can we learn from Covid-19.	M32	
ECREA 7th International Crisis Communication Conference: Crisis Communication from a Citizen Perspective – Urban Risks and Crises	M36	

	1st session of the permanent group of gender and politics. Spanish Association of Political Science	M36
	ASDR Naturgefahrenstagung 2023	M36
	UNESCO Global Media and Information Literacy Conference	M36
Conferences (Attended)	3rd 'Nicosia Risk Forum' - Regional Collaboration in Societal Safety"	M1
	Emergenza pandemia: quale impatto su natalità e nuove generazioni? Presentazione del rapporto a cura del gruppo di esperti su demografia e COVID-19	M2
	Northern Network of Medical Humanities Congress 2021	M6
	57 Scientific Meeting of the SIEDS (Società Italiana di Economia, Demografia e Statistica)	M7
	Annual International conference Royal Geographical Society with IBG 2021	M10
	Lisbon Forum 2021: Intercultural dialogue in the infodemic era	M12
	Pandemie symposium (Pandemic symposium)	M17
	Royal Geographical Society with IBG 2022, Newcastle	M22
	Northern Network of Medical Humanities Congress 2023	M30
	LSE Commission for Pandemic Governance and Inequalities 2023	M32
Other events (Webinars)	How media and authorities handled the Corona crisis	M0
	NO FEAR webinar on Human Resources management during COVID19	M2
	NO-FEAR webinar on risk communication	M2
	NO FEAR webinar on Supply Chain Challenges during COVID 19	M5
	Minverva Lab Seminars: "COVID-19 and the overlap between job and home responsibilities: new evidence from the U.S. and Italy"	M5
	Scandinavian Pandemic Response: Perspectives on Crisis Communication During the Pandemic in Nordic Countries	M5
	NO FEAR webinar on COVID in children	M6
	The impact of Covid-19 and community responses webinar organized	M6
	NO-FEAR and COVINFORM joint webinar on vaccination hesitancy among healthcare workers	M7
	Webinar for Dept. of occupational health science and psychology and for Academy for health and occupational life, University of Gävle.	M12
	Invited presenter at webinar organized by CRISCOM (civil society organization)	M15
Webinar with Publicistklubben East (journalists' association)	M16	

	Public Health Network Cymru Webinar	M21
Other events (physical and virtual)	COVID-19 2C projects cluster meeting	M3
	Empowering R&I collaboration to respond to the socio-economic challenges of the coronavirus pandemic	M3
	Sharing Marginalised Stories: Pandemic Projects from Swansea	M4
	Invited presenter at "The Media meeting" (Mediemötet), Borås Tidning/UGOT	M7
	Coronavirus and People with Learning Disabilities Study	M7
	Invited presenter at a working meeting at the Swedish Corona Commission	M8
	Pandemic concerns in high trust societies - COVID-19 Lessons learned, organised by Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency	M9
	Gender and COVID-19: Close-to-community providers in fragile settings and vulnerable communities during crisis	M11
	Official Launch of the Welsh Association of Physicians of African and Caribbean Origins (WAPACO)	M13
	Crisis Cooperation 2021 - arranged by West Sweden Region Council	M13
	"Health, Diversity and Covid-19" A conversation with Rohini Mathur (London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine), Orkan Okan (Technical University of Munich) and Katharina Crepaz (Eurac Research)	M15
	Policy Area Secure Steering Group Meeting	M26
	Meeting and discussion results Health Department Municipality of Antwerp and University of Antwerp	M32
	ERA Forum Workshop: R&I gaps, needs and challenges with respect to the twin (digital & green) transitions and their impact on vulnerable workers	M36
Festival della Statistica e della Demografia	M36	
Other events (workshop attended)	Presentation Workshop: "Emotional impact (both professional and personal) in front-line emergency healthcare workers during COVID-19 pandemic"	M6
	CERIS innovation workshop: European Resilience in case of Pandemics 22/04/2021	M6
	Empowering R&I collaboration to respond to the socio-economic challenges of the coronavirus pandemic	M12
	Research to Policy Meeting: COVID-19 social and behavioural studies	M12
	Strategic decision-making during COVID-19 (Hearing Swedish Defense University)	M13
	5th Research to Policy Meeting	M14

	6th Research to Policy Meeting	M17
	Joint final event- ENOTICE, PROACTIVE, PANDEM-2	M32
	MDA internal meeting of the Medical Department	M35
	„CAVE! Weniger vulnerabel in der Krise“	M35
Workshops (organized)	Scandinavian Pandemic Response: Perspectives on Crisis Communication During the Pandemic in Nordic Countries	M5
	Workshop for Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic.	M6
	Workshop for Horizon 2020 projects focusing on socio-economic and behavioural consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic.	M12
	COVINFORM workshop: Two workshops with the participation of MDA staff and volunteers, to present the project's findings and collect practitioners feedback	M32
	COVINFORM workshop: Three workshops with the participation of MDA staff and volunteers, to present the project's findings and collect practitioners feedback	M33
	COVINFORM workshop: Eight organised by SNCR with doctors to discuss the intervention and the challenges during the last years in the COVID-19 context	M32

ANNEX V. COVINFORM CRISIS MANAGEMENT PLAN

A crisis situation is any event that disturbs the normal course of our actions, which could seriously damage the brand of our project and its reputation, as well as the credibility of our consortium and the organizations and institutions constituting our consortium. Sometimes a crisis can be foreseen, others will arrive without warning. In either case, the key to resolving such a situation will be the way we handle it and communicate internally. This management is ineluctably due to a previously planned communication plan that allows us to act quickly. The crisis does not wait for us to plan our strategy – therefore, we must plan it ahead, even before we are faced with a crisis. As such, the following provides guidance on activities to avoid, and, if unavoidable, on how to react to a crisis.

Before the crisis

This stage is fundamental for the development and resolution of the problems that we may encounter during the crisis. At this stage, it is crucial to ensure that the consortium understands and agrees on an appropriate communication strategy in case of crises. To be well set up in times of crisis the project partners agreed on implementing the following strategies at the beginning of their collaboration.

- Define and develop a network of contacts and allies that will help us to develop and disseminate the results of our project. With them we will maintain a smooth and periodic communication;
- Establish relationships with media and journalists that allow us to promote our project. This prior contact, through press releases, newsletters or opinion articles, will allow us to have a relationship that avoids distrust to a certain extent;
- In the same way, we have to act in social networks, developing a good communication strategy that establishes the loyalty of our followers and expands the followers' network. Twitter is usually the first place where we will get aware of a critical situation;
- In the time before the crisis, all partners should be trained in how to effectively broadcast messages in the media;
- In the same way, the communication and dissemination leaders, SYNYO and TRI, should develop a compact and coordinated team to avoid situations of lack of coordination, the duplicity of actions, contradiction of messages or lack of information in certain areas where the project operates.

During the crisis

Should a crisis occur, our first action will be to set up a Crisis Committee and to go to the public with an institutional statement that will be spread on our website and social networks. The first contact point is the coordinator (SYNYO) and the dissemination leader (TRI), who will set up the Crisis Committee. Our speed will avoid the most dangerous thing that exists in a crisis: the 'rumour'. If we do not inform, the public and networks will look

elsewhere. And although the speed of response is paramount, it is equally important that our output does not comment on any kind of failures or contradictions. Hence, our precision and caution in everything we distribute are crucial. The coordinator, together with the dissemination leader, should guide the crisis communication strategy and communicate it to all partners. Our initial statement will respond by providing our name, organization, project and confirmation of the incident, referring to subsequent communications from our organization. This first release will give us some time to gather information and learn more about what happened.

After the crisis

'After' time corresponds to the overall evaluation period of the effectiveness of our crisis plan and its implementation, and consequentially an update and improvement of specific steps. This time is also important for our consortium because the assessment we make of our performance throughout the process will allow us to adjust our crisis plan for future cases. The assessment will help us to evaluate our communication actions during normal periods of the project.

ANNEX VI Social Media Engagement

1. LinkedIn:

Impressions from 31.10.2022 -> Data can only be exported for this period.

Platform	Date	Impressions
LinkedIn	31.10.22	46
LinkedIn	01.11.22	48
LinkedIn	02.11.22	61
LinkedIn	03.11.22	144
LinkedIn	04.11.22	58
LinkedIn	05.11.22	58
LinkedIn	06.11.22	37
LinkedIn	07.11.22	37
LinkedIn	08.11.22	19
LinkedIn	09.11.22	13
LinkedIn	10.11.22	72
LinkedIn	11.11.22	32
LinkedIn	12.11.22	15
LinkedIn	13.11.22	14
LinkedIn	14.11.22	10
LinkedIn	15.11.22	16
LinkedIn	16.11.22	171
LinkedIn	17.11.22	105
LinkedIn	18.11.22	38
LinkedIn	19.11.22	40
LinkedIn	20.11.22	21
LinkedIn	21.11.22	18
LinkedIn	22.11.22	22
LinkedIn	23.11.22	199
LinkedIn	24.11.22	73
LinkedIn	25.11.22	193
LinkedIn	26.11.22	42

LinkedIn	27.11.22	23
LinkedIn	28.11.22	32
LinkedIn	29.11.22	125
LinkedIn	30.11.22	80
LinkedIn	01.12.22	39
LinkedIn	02.12.22	30
LinkedIn	03.12.22	18
LinkedIn	04.12.22	28
LinkedIn	05.12.22	50
LinkedIn	06.12.22	24
LinkedIn	07.12.22	122
LinkedIn	08.12.22	41
LinkedIn	09.12.22	60
LinkedIn	10.12.22	57
LinkedIn	11.12.22	88
LinkedIn	12.12.22	45
LinkedIn	13.12.22	13
LinkedIn	14.12.22	206
LinkedIn	15.12.22	69
LinkedIn	16.12.22	52
LinkedIn	17.12.22	25
LinkedIn	18.12.22	29
LinkedIn	19.12.22	32
LinkedIn	20.12.22	21
LinkedIn	21.12.22	42
LinkedIn	22.12.22	14
LinkedIn	23.12.22	137
LinkedIn	24.12.22	11
LinkedIn	25.12.22	5
LinkedIn	26.12.22	8
LinkedIn	27.12.22	12
LinkedIn	28.12.22	6
LinkedIn	29.12.22	4
LinkedIn	30.12.22	31

LinkedIn	31.12.22	3
LinkedIn	01.01.23	6
LinkedIn	02.01.23	11
LinkedIn	03.01.23	15
LinkedIn	04.01.23	6
LinkedIn	05.01.23	4
LinkedIn	06.01.23	4
LinkedIn	07.01.23	22
LinkedIn	08.01.23	7
LinkedIn	09.01.23	10
LinkedIn	10.01.23	4
LinkedIn	11.01.23	8
LinkedIn	12.01.23	10
LinkedIn	13.01.23	3
LinkedIn	14.01.23	0
LinkedIn	15.01.23	1
LinkedIn	16.01.23	2
LinkedIn	17.01.23	12
LinkedIn	18.01.23	4
LinkedIn	19.01.23	1
LinkedIn	20.01.23	0
LinkedIn	21.01.23	0
LinkedIn	22.01.23	0
LinkedIn	23.01.23	7
LinkedIn	24.01.23	0
LinkedIn	25.01.23	0
LinkedIn	26.01.23	0
LinkedIn	27.01.23	4
LinkedIn	28.01.23	2
LinkedIn	29.01.23	0
LinkedIn	30.01.23	1
LinkedIn	31.01.23	350
LinkedIn	01.02.23	165
LinkedIn	02.02.23	82

LinkedIn	03.02.23	47
LinkedIn	04.02.23	34
LinkedIn	05.02.23	21
LinkedIn	06.02.23	66
LinkedIn	07.02.23	27
LinkedIn	08.02.23	27
LinkedIn	09.02.23	256
LinkedIn	10.02.23	68
LinkedIn	11.02.23	49
LinkedIn	12.02.23	26
LinkedIn	13.02.23	60
LinkedIn	14.02.23	25
LinkedIn	15.02.23	24
LinkedIn	16.02.23	21
LinkedIn	17.02.23	60
LinkedIn	18.02.23	15
LinkedIn	19.02.23	17
LinkedIn	20.02.23	234
LinkedIn	21.02.23	62
LinkedIn	22.02.23	125
LinkedIn	23.02.23	48
LinkedIn	24.02.23	39
LinkedIn	25.02.23	13
LinkedIn	26.02.23	23
LinkedIn	27.02.23	15
LinkedIn	28.02.23	293
LinkedIn	01.03.23	87
LinkedIn	02.03.23	54
LinkedIn	03.03.23	55
LinkedIn	04.03.23	40
LinkedIn	05.03.23	39
LinkedIn	06.03.23	59
LinkedIn	07.03.23	84
LinkedIn	08.03.23	304

LinkedIn	09.03.23	102
LinkedIn	10.03.23	91
LinkedIn	11.03.23	51
LinkedIn	12.03.23	89
LinkedIn	13.03.23	82
LinkedIn	14.03.23	157
LinkedIn	15.03.23	213
LinkedIn	16.03.23	78
LinkedIn	17.03.23	51
LinkedIn	18.03.23	23
LinkedIn	19.03.23	39
LinkedIn	20.03.23	50
LinkedIn	21.03.23	38
LinkedIn	22.03.23	229
LinkedIn	23.03.23	91
LinkedIn	24.03.23	28
LinkedIn	25.03.23	20
LinkedIn	26.03.23	17
LinkedIn	27.03.23	24
LinkedIn	28.03.23	67
LinkedIn	29.03.23	50
LinkedIn	30.03.23	42
LinkedIn	31.03.23	0
LinkedIn	01.04.23	0
LinkedIn	02.04.23	0
LinkedIn	03.04.23	0
LinkedIn	04.04.23	1
LinkedIn	05.04.23	7
LinkedIn	06.04.23	0
LinkedIn	07.04.23	0
LinkedIn	08.04.23	0
LinkedIn	09.04.23	0
LinkedIn	10.04.23	0
LinkedIn	11.04.23	0

LinkedIn	12.04.23	0
LinkedIn	13.04.23	0
LinkedIn	14.04.23	0
LinkedIn	15.04.23	0
LinkedIn	16.04.23	0
LinkedIn	17.04.23	0
LinkedIn	18.04.23	258
LinkedIn	19.04.23	87
LinkedIn	20.04.23	23
LinkedIn	21.04.23	8
LinkedIn	22.04.23	7
LinkedIn	23.04.23	2
LinkedIn	24.04.23	6
LinkedIn	25.04.23	12
LinkedIn	26.04.23	4
LinkedIn	27.04.23	123
LinkedIn	28.04.23	43
LinkedIn	29.04.23	17
LinkedIn	30.04.23	23
LinkedIn	01.05.23	9
LinkedIn	02.05.23	123
LinkedIn	03.05.23	47
LinkedIn	04.05.23	22
LinkedIn	05.05.23	6
LinkedIn	06.05.23	3
LinkedIn	07.05.23	1
LinkedIn	08.05.23	8
LinkedIn	09.05.23	6
LinkedIn	10.05.23	5
LinkedIn	11.05.23	10
LinkedIn	12.05.23	2
LinkedIn	13.05.23	26
LinkedIn	14.05.23	7
LinkedIn	15.05.23	4

LinkedIn	16.05.23	1
LinkedIn	17.05.23	2
LinkedIn	18.05.23	1
LinkedIn	19.05.23	2
LinkedIn	20.05.23	2
LinkedIn	21.05.23	0
LinkedIn	22.05.23	5
LinkedIn	23.05.23	2
LinkedIn	24.05.23	84
LinkedIn	25.05.23	60
LinkedIn	26.05.23	91
LinkedIn	27.05.23	70
LinkedIn	28.05.23	37
LinkedIn	29.05.23	29
LinkedIn	30.05.23	24
LinkedIn	31.05.23	34
LinkedIn	01.06.23	30
LinkedIn	02.06.23	85
LinkedIn	03.06.23	68
LinkedIn	04.06.23	11
LinkedIn	05.06.23	17
LinkedIn	06.06.23	55
LinkedIn	07.06.23	53
LinkedIn	08.06.23	3
LinkedIn	09.06.23	8
LinkedIn	10.06.23	8
LinkedIn	11.06.23	7
LinkedIn	12.06.23	11
LinkedIn	13.06.23	2
LinkedIn	14.06.23	233
LinkedIn	15.06.23	216
LinkedIn	16.06.23	71
LinkedIn	17.06.23	63
LinkedIn	18.06.23	35

LinkedIn	19.06.23	49
LinkedIn	20.06.23	75
LinkedIn	21.06.23	107
LinkedIn	22.06.23	54
LinkedIn	23.06.23	105
LinkedIn	24.06.23	102
LinkedIn	25.06.23	62
LinkedIn	26.06.23	39
LinkedIn	27.06.23	32
LinkedIn	28.06.23	24
LinkedIn	29.06.23	17
LinkedIn	30.06.23	188
LinkedIn	01.07.23	40
LinkedIn	02.07.23	28
LinkedIn	03.07.23	30
LinkedIn	04.07.23	24
LinkedIn	05.07.23	20
LinkedIn	06.07.23	22
LinkedIn	07.07.23	26
LinkedIn	08.07.23	2
LinkedIn	09.07.23	21
LinkedIn	10.07.23	10
LinkedIn	11.07.23	36
LinkedIn	12.07.23	12
LinkedIn	13.07.23	22
LinkedIn	14.07.23	140
LinkedIn	15.07.23	14
LinkedIn	16.07.23	18
LinkedIn	17.07.23	275
LinkedIn	18.07.23	65
LinkedIn	19.07.23	186
LinkedIn	20.07.23	204
LinkedIn	21.07.23	60
LinkedIn	22.07.23	34

LinkedIn	23.07.23	31
LinkedIn	24.07.23	27
LinkedIn	25.07.23	22
LinkedIn	26.07.23	93
LinkedIn	27.07.23	131
LinkedIn	28.07.23	74
LinkedIn	29.07.23	29
LinkedIn	30.07.23	11
LinkedIn	31.07.23	42
LinkedIn	01.08.23	14
LinkedIn	02.08.23	27
LinkedIn	03.08.23	99
LinkedIn	04.08.23	18
LinkedIn	05.08.23	27
LinkedIn	06.08.23	15
LinkedIn	07.08.23	55
LinkedIn	08.08.23	28
LinkedIn	09.08.23	83
LinkedIn	10.08.23	19
LinkedIn	11.08.23	90
LinkedIn	12.08.23	35
LinkedIn	13.08.23	37
LinkedIn	14.08.23	36
LinkedIn	15.08.23	13
LinkedIn	16.08.23	18
LinkedIn	17.08.23	78
LinkedIn	18.08.23	18
LinkedIn	19.08.23	10
LinkedIn	20.08.23	5
LinkedIn	21.08.23	33
LinkedIn	22.08.23	26
LinkedIn	23.08.23	148
LinkedIn	24.08.23	48
LinkedIn	25.08.23	55

LinkedIn	26.08.23	26
LinkedIn	27.08.23	14
LinkedIn	28.08.23	58
LinkedIn	29.08.23	29
LinkedIn	30.08.23	83
LinkedIn	31.08.23	19
LinkedIn	01.09.23	8
LinkedIn	02.09.23	9
LinkedIn	03.09.23	4
LinkedIn	04.09.23	7
LinkedIn	05.09.23	11
LinkedIn	06.09.23	9
LinkedIn	07.09.23	143
LinkedIn	08.09.23	175
LinkedIn	09.09.23	37
LinkedIn	10.09.23	34
LinkedIn	11.09.23	48
LinkedIn	12.09.23	36
LinkedIn	13.09.23	18
LinkedIn	14.09.23	11
LinkedIn	15.09.23	24
LinkedIn	16.09.23	3
LinkedIn	17.09.23	1
LinkedIn	18.09.23	0
LinkedIn	19.09.23	8
LinkedIn	20.09.23	3
LinkedIn	21.09.23	4
LinkedIn	22.09.23	5
LinkedIn	23.09.23	12
LinkedIn	24.09.23	6
LinkedIn	25.09.23	19
LinkedIn	26.09.23	7
LinkedIn	27.09.23	21
LinkedIn	28.09.23	233

LinkedIn	29.09.23	86
LinkedIn	30.09.23	45
LinkedIn	01.10.23	39
LinkedIn	02.10.23	23
LinkedIn	03.10.23	234
LinkedIn	04.10.23	125
LinkedIn	05.10.23	36
LinkedIn	06.10.23	37
LinkedIn	07.10.23	33
LinkedIn	08.10.23	22
LinkedIn	09.10.23	15
LinkedIn	10.10.23	15
LinkedIn	11.10.23	17
LinkedIn	12.10.23	105
LinkedIn	13.10.23	21
LinkedIn	14.10.23	22
LinkedIn	15.10.23	18
LinkedIn	16.10.23	16
LinkedIn	17.10.23	133
LinkedIn	18.10.23	58
LinkedIn	19.10.23	142
LinkedIn	20.10.23	113
LinkedIn	21.10.23	39
LinkedIn	22.10.23	67
LinkedIn	23.10.23	644
LinkedIn	24.10.23	110
LinkedIn	25.10.23	269
LinkedIn	26.10.23	56
LinkedIn	27.10.23	223
LinkedIn	28.10.23	137
LinkedIn	29.10.23	56
LinkedIn	30.10.23	256

2. Top 50 posts on LinkedIn during this period

Platform	Post publish date	Impressions
LinkedIn	31.01.23	969
LinkedIn	19.10.23	947
LinkedIn	28.02.23	636
LinkedIn	08.03.23	609
LinkedIn	09.02.23	559
LinkedIn	14.06.23	558
LinkedIn	07.09.23	558
LinkedIn	28.09.23	556
LinkedIn	14.12.22	554
LinkedIn	07.12.22	457
LinkedIn	03.10.23	424
LinkedIn	22.03.23	417
LinkedIn	23.06.23	412
LinkedIn	25.11.22	394
LinkedIn	14.03.23	393
LinkedIn	26.05.23	389
LinkedIn	20.02.23	388

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LinkedIn	16.11.22	388
LinkedIn	23.11.22	379
LinkedIn	17.08.23	357
LinkedIn	25.10.22	344
LinkedIn	17.10.23	340
LinkedIn	23.08.23	327
LinkedIn	17.07.23	316
LinkedIn	25.10.23	299
LinkedIn	19.07.23	298
LinkedIn	03.11.22	286
LinkedIn	26.07.23	275
LinkedIn	02.06.23	265
LinkedIn	30.06.23	258
LinkedIn	29.11.22	246
LinkedIn	07.03.23	239
LinkedIn	27.04.23	236
LinkedIn	14.07.23	235
LinkedIn	18.04.23	232
LinkedIn	11.08.23	231
LinkedIn	15.06.23	226
LinkedIn	02.05.23	221
LinkedIn	27.07.23	219
LinkedIn	03.08.23	207
LinkedIn	24.05.23	203
LinkedIn	15.03.23	197
LinkedIn	22.02.23	196
LinkedIn	29.06.23	190
LinkedIn	21.06.23	183
LinkedIn	12.10.23	181

LinkedIn	27.10.23	177
LinkedIn	24.10.23	175
LinkedIn	20.07.23	168
LinkedIn	05.04.23	151

3. X (Twitter):

Impressions and likes from 04.10.2022 -> Data can only be exported for this period.

Platform	Post publish date	Impressions	Likes
Twitter	04.10.22	7.0	4.0
Twitter	07.10.22	106.0	6.0
Twitter	11.10.22	15.0	16.0
Twitter	19.10.22	25.0	4.0
Twitter	21.10.22	36.0	7.0
Twitter	24.10.22	33.0	2.0
Twitter	25.10.22	41.0	7.0
Twitter	03.11.22	89.0	4.0
Twitter	16.11.22	59.0	3.0
Twitter	23.11.22	199.0	6.0
Twitter	25.11.22	62.0	2.0
Twitter	29.11.22	111.0	2.0
Twitter	07.12.22	85.0	4.0
Twitter	13.12.22	495.0	8.0
Twitter	22.12.22	162.0	8.0
Twitter	10.01.23	100.0	3.0
Twitter	31.01.23	180.0	2.0

Twitter	02.02.23	223.0	9.0
Twitter	09.02.23	32.0	1.0
Twitter	20.02.23	509.0	5.0
Twitter	22.02.23	449.0	7.0
Twitter	28.02.23	219.0	8.0
Twitter	07.03.23	91.0	3.0
Twitter	08.03.23	134.0	4.0
Twitter	14.03.23	210.0	9.0
Twitter	15.03.23	82.0	2.0
Twitter	22.03.23	143.0	4.0
Twitter	04.04.23	151.0	3.0
Twitter	05.04.23	741.0	2.0
Twitter	18.04.23	104.0	2.0
Twitter	27.04.23	122.0	3.0
Twitter	02.05.23	157.0	7.0
Twitter	24.05.23	106.0	6.0
Twitter	26.05.23	78.0	3.0
Twitter	02.06.23	204.0	5.0
Twitter	14.06.23	177.0	7.0
Twitter	15.06.23	61.0	2.0
Twitter	21.06.23	100.0	3.0
Twitter	23.06.23	135.0	5.0
Twitter	29.06.23	102.0	2.0
Twitter	30.06.23	90.0	3.0
Twitter	17.07.23	243.0	8.0
Twitter	18.07.23	105.0	6.0
Twitter	19.07.23	62.0	2.0
Twitter	20.07.23	73.0	1.0
Twitter	26.07.23	82.0	3.0

Twitter	27.07.23	63.0	2.0
Twitter	03.08.23	106.0	2.0
Twitter	11.08.23	69.0	0.0
Twitter	17.08.23	439.0	6.0
Twitter	23.08.23	106.0	5.0
Twitter	07.09.23	180.0	10.0
Twitter	28.09.23	47.0	1.0
Twitter	19.10.23	20.0	0.0
Twitter	25.10.23	27.0	3.0
Twitter	27.10.23	61.0	2.0
Twitter	30.10.23	11.0	0.0

4. Instagram*:

Platform	Post publish date	Likes
Instagram	01.06.22	11
Instagram	07.06.22	8
Instagram	13.06.22	10
Instagram	15.06.22	11
Instagram	21.06.22	9
Instagram	27.06.22	8
Instagram	29.06.22	10
Instagram	19.07.22	10
Instagram	21.07.22	10
Instagram	25.07.22	11
Instagram	28.07.22	10
Instagram	04.08.22	12
Instagram	09.08.22	9

Instagram	17.08.22	10
Instagram	19.08.22	5
Instagram	31.08.22	7
Instagram	07.09.22	8
Instagram	13.09.22	6
Instagram	15.09.22	5
Instagram	21.09.22	3
Instagram	29.09.22	7
Instagram	07.10.22	6
Instagram	19.10.22	3
Instagram	21.10.22	7
Instagram	24.10.22	4
Instagram	25.10.22	27
Instagram	03.11.22	5
Instagram	25.11.22	7
Instagram	07.12.22	5
Instagram	14.12.22	4
Instagram	06.01.23	4
Instagram	09.02.23	5
Instagram	28.02.23	4
Instagram	08.03.23	4
Instagram	09.03.23	4
Instagram	10.03.23	3
Instagram	22.03.23	4
Instagram	04.04.23	4
Instagram	18.04.23	4
Instagram	02.05.23	5
Instagram	02.06.23	4
Instagram	14.06.23	8

Instagram	15.06.23	1
Instagram	21.06.23	5
Instagram	23.06.23	3
Instagram	30.06.23	8
Instagram	17.07.23	6
Instagram	19.07.23	3
Instagram	20.07.23	6
Instagram	26.07.23	4
Instagram	03.08.23	3
Instagram	11.08.23	6
Instagram	17.08.23	5
Instagram	28.09.23	3
Instagram	12.10.23	4
Instagram	17.10.23	11
Instagram	19.10.23	8
Instagram	24.10.23	6
Instagram	25.10.23	5
Instagram	27.10.23	6
Instagram	30.10.23	2

*we introduced Instagram only in mid-2022 to our social media schedule.